

Abstract

In the analysis of the Solar System¹ in the context of Complete Relativity² (CR) planetary neurogenesis has been hypothesized and discussed with some strong evidence provided. Here, the 6th major event of Earth's neurogenesis is discussed, correlated with ancient prophecies, religions and great pyramids in Giza, Egypt.

Judgement day 6

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1 Predefinitions

1.1 Prophecy

A prophecy is any prediction of an event supposed to happen some time in the future. It may be supplemented with timing and additional details on the event.

In order to be true, a prophecy must be relative. Thus, any true prophecy can describe an event of a local future only if such event has already occurred somewhere sometime - in a correlated environment. The accuracy or strength of the prophecy will then depend on the strength of correlation.

While prophecies can be extremely accurate, no two environments are absolutely equal, therefore uncertainty always exists in any prophecy.

Due to inherently cyclic nature of large and small-scale phenomena a prophecy can be based on the analysis of past events in the local environment. Timing of the predicted events can be hard, however, large scale events are usually preceded by correlated small-scale events, therefore, these can be interpreted as precursors, signs, or signals, of upcoming large scale events.

1.2 Prophet

A prophet is the author of an prophecy, the one predicting correlation between the announced future event and a past event. The past event represents a relative vision of the future event. This vision may be, in part, relatively invariant to the prophet (e.g., a result of non-biased scientific observation, analysis and computation) but it is also based on the employed logic (possibly based on experience) of the prophet, which may be biased. A vision with most probability to become true is, thus, a vision of an *experienced* and non-biased prophet, with the amount of possible different interpretations minimized. A vision does not have to be a result of conscious synthesis or computation, it can be a subconsciously constructed hallucination (e.g., a dream), in which case the mind itself can serve as a scientific instrument (this is not pseudo-science, subconsciousness can be correlated with relative precognition/causality, which is also expectable

in the context of evolution). However, here, the precision/ambiguity of the instrument is strongly dependent on species/subspecies and the individual. In human species (especially civilized), reliable such instruments are probably rare. Those with a longer range in space/time are even rarer, due to prevalence of short-term interests. Therefore, any subconsciously constructed vision should be *consumed* with caveats. In a reliable subconscious companion (or layer of self), these visions can be generally reliable as well, however, timing and interpretation of such visions is generally a result of conscious logic and experience, which may not be as reliable - affecting the prophet's credibility. Consciousness operates on different timescales than the subconscious and is prone to contraction and dilation of time intervals, due to bias. Even with no bias, the prophet and the population (environment) are often out of phase - so the timing may be correct but is incorrectly applied to global environment/population rather than to the limited environment of the prophet. A *raw* message of a prophet (e.g., the one expressed while the prophet is in some state of trance) generally should not be taken literally. In such messages words have different and context-dependent meanings, and time intervals such as centuries or millennia can become hours or days. Therefore, relativistic corrections must be applied to any conscious interpretation. The corrections can be applied by the prophet himself once out of trance or out of the vision (note that a vision can also materialize in a dream in mature prophets, not requiring trance), backing up the prophecy through sound philosophy or scientific research, analyses, theories and hypotheses.

A good example of the above mentioned misalignment are the prophecies of Jesus. When he announced the apocalypse he was announcing his own apocalypse (culminating in death), even though he himself consciously believed that a global one is imminent. This does not mean that he did not see the global apocalypse in his vision - he did, he simply incorrectly applied the timing of a limited precursor apocalypse to the global one. The reason for this is that he was in the middle of transformation of consciousness, when an individual's mind is completely out of phase with the population. So much so, that its expression is commonly interpreted as psychosis (although in this case, a prolonged state of *trance* is probably a more appropriate description).

It's probably possible for an individual to be born as a prophet. In human species, however, one probably generally has to mature into a prophet through this transformation.

I wouldn't say that Jesus was delusional at the time (certainly not absolutely), the envisioned global apocalypse will happen, he just experienced it ahead of *everyone* else. I'd also say that anyone who believes that Jesus, or any other well-known prophet, was some all-mighty god is delusional. Yes, such people are relatively special people, but I wouldn't call them gods, rather messengers of gods, or messengers of truth (at least with relativistic corrections, or proper reference frames, applied). How-

ever, if the prophet is out of phase with population during soul transformation, one could question who is he aligned with? During these limited times, one could argue that the prophet is well aligned with some god and then conceptualize trinity - the equivalence of the man, god, and the holy spirit, where this spirit would be the alignment or the superposition of the two souls. But why stop at trinity? A man could be aligned with multiple gods (of different scale) and, thus be, effectively, a messenger of gods, rather than a single god.

During the trance of my own transformation I have convinced myself that the world will end exactly on 2018.07.01. Of course, the world did not end at the time, but I did (or, *my* world did). This date marked the end of my transformation, when my old self was finally dead and I was reborn as a new person. I was very close to the permanent decoupling of the soul from the body (*classical* death), having even lost consciousness on one occasion (which I interpret as a temporary decoupling of the soul from the body), but the coupling survived. However, after one survives such transformation, many years [of study and experience] need to pass for one to mature into a reliable interpreter of visions (similar to the maturation of a newborn child) - if one chooses that path (although the choice is relative, it may be equally valid to say that the one was chosen for the role).

If one is to correlate prophets with gods, however, from a scientific perspective (or, a perspective of anyone interested in truth), a realistic definition of a god is necessary. Per my definition in CR, a lifeform whose rest mass is multiple orders of magnitude greater than life that lives on it and in it, is, for that life, a god. Now, it is well known that we can influence our bodies with our minds (resulting in, for example, expression of specific hormones). This is a consequence of subconscious communication between a relative god (our soul or mind, highly correlated with the brain) and the smaller lifeforms living in its body (e.g., souls associated with cells, microbes, or even smaller entities). Note that the same parts of the brain are active when two people are thinking of the same thing while speaking different languages. This strongly suggests that a communication between individuals, or even species, speaking different languages is possible, even if not on conscious level. Thus, probably some universal language exists for inter-scalar communication between entangled souls, however, it will always be prone to misinterpretation on the level associated with expression, proportionally to the amount of misalignment between the god and the messenger in the associated scale-invariant framework describing the state of mind. The alignment is possible because the universes (scales) are self-similar, however, relativistic space-time corrections must be applied because they're not absolutely equal. If we are gods speaking through messengers in our bodies, who is the god most likely to be speaking through human prophets?

Planet Earth, obviously. The god is probably not speaking specifically, or consciously, to any individual, however. The prophets are simply those willing and capable to listen. And mature ones are those willing and capable to understand (properly interpret the message) and act on it. In other words, most of us probably have the capability to tune in to the frequency of god (per my theories, our souls are the quanta forming space of the god's soul - a mediators of force/communication evolved from the coupling of more fundamental forces, such as gravity and electro-magnetism), but not many of us are willing to do so, and even smaller number of us is unafraid to understand and express the message through deeds (embodiment of words).

Mental alignment of a prophet with god is not limited to the reception of messages - this should be a two-way communication. In this context, as noted before, one could argue that the great alignment (or harmony) with god is equivalent to the notion that god exists at multiple different scales and, thus, claim that Jesus, for example, was a god to people at such times (in addition to being a god to the beings forming his body). It should be clear, however, that it is then equally valid to say that the greater god was Jesus at these times, or a man. "Son of man" (as Jesus may have called himself during transformation, and thus should not be taken literally) then equals to "son of god", and the "son" here should be interpreted as the "sun" or the "soul" (per my theories, Sun is the soul of the Solar System). One can then speak of duality, trinity or *n-ity* of a prophet, but the notion should clearly be taken as relative. Out of interest, some take it absolutely, claiming then that the god is almighty and that the man can be an almighty god himself. But instead, this *equality* tells us that god is not infallible and his *immortality* is proportional to inter-scalar harmony. Jesus did not chose to die and sacrifice himself for human sins, he died due to the overwhelming human disharmony manifesting itself as sins against him [and] against god. Neither the church, nor the zealots want for god to speak his mind through a human mind, they need the messenger dead so they can put words into its mouth, then sell these words to the masses. This is how cancer operates, and with the obedient masses, this is how cancer thrives.

1.3 The point of no return

In the context of current climate, the point of no return is the point when climate changes become irreversible.

In the context of this paper, it is not only the point when climate changes become irreversible it is also the point when actions leading to *extinction* of surface life in the process of planetary neurogenesis become irreversible.

Some might argue that this point has not been reached yet, however, even

if that is the case, it is clear that we're not moving away from that point rather towards it. Predictions of modern science usually tend to be either overly conservative or overly alarming. The reason for both is a general lack of holism in the approach, and the underlying reason for that are the short-term interests of the parties involved in the process. There are different levels where this bias can be expressed - at the level of governments/companies/industries sponsoring the research, at the various levels of the academy (scientists doing the measurements, scientists doing the analyses, ...), publishing companies (editors, reviewers, ...), news agencies and outlets (editors, authors, ...). The question is not whether bias exists, the question is which bias will prevail overall. Climate and environment are both deeply correlated with economy. Since the growth of the economy is prioritized at the highest levels of the hierarchy (but often at the lower levels as well), it is not hard to conclude which bias will prevail in which case. Predictions and decisions are based on modelling. And the truth is that there is a lot of uncertainty in models, however, if the profit is in the downplaying of danger, the predictions will be conservative, otherwise alarming. In any case, the policies will be based on these predictions, completely disregarding uncertainties and other possibilities. Neutral assessment of the situation can mainly be found in independent analyses where profit does not trump truth, rarely in the mainstream, regardless of the level.

What is the truth? The truth is that the apocalypse is most likely ahead, regardless of the prevailing bias. This is because climate and the biosphere/environment are intrinsically and intricately connected. Those who are downplaying climate changes tend to put the emphasis on the biosphere (e.g., the current US president seems to be concerned about whales and human lives, not at all about climate), while those who seem to prioritize climate tend to downplay the influence on the biosphere (e.g., whales are fine as long as the noisy boats are electric). In other words, there are no holistic approaches, at least no genuinely holistic ones. Infinite growth of the economy and the population cannot be sustainable and healthy, regardless of the source of energy. Most of the population, however, probably believes that the apocalypse is ahead, however, bias is evident here as well - they either believe it is still far away, or right about the corner. Either way, it serves as another excuse for their own irresponsibility, with a similar difference in flavour - some *prioritize* climate, others environment/biosphere (even though all this is intimately connected) - but even here most are prioritizing humans and human environments, some claim to care for all but effectively they do not. I am not part of the mainstream, [but] I am a genuine seeker of truth, and as such, I spend most of my time researching, analysing, calculating and modelling. In the process I am exposed to subconscious guidance (incl. subconsciously constructed visions) but the emphasis is on the classical scientific method - even if not on the orthodox paradigms. Regarding the apocalypse - in the form of extinction of life on Earth's surface, I have 3 models based on my overall research, the main difference being in timing. Sorted by probability, from highest to lowest:

1. 21st century, centred about the year 2066 if not sooner,

2. 24th century,
3. beyond the 24th century.

One should understand the above as 3 base states, so the answer is in the superposition.

The 21st century estimate is based on the theory of planetary neurogenesis, the 24th century is based on the assumption that humans represent a malignant cancer for Earth, the 3rd is the *null hypothesis*. Superposition here implies that some life will be gone from Earth's surface in the 21st century, some will continue and survive until the 24th century and then some will remain as long as Earth remains alive. I believe that the life that will be gone in the 21st century is the polarized life, neutral complex life might continue living on the surface for a few centuries more, but beyond the 24th century only microbes will remain.

The above is based on the assumption that the point of no return has been passed or that it will be passed (I see no reason to believe otherwise, but I see plenty of reason to believe it already has been passed, *at least* effectively, but of course, I could be wrong). Therefore, I interpret the reports of modern science on the state of climate/environment[3] simply as updates on the progress towards the apocalypse. I am not a pessimist, I do not see death on the level of an individual as something absolutely bad and I don't see death on the level of population as something absolutely bad. I believe in reincarnation so I don't believe the population will be forever gone. I believe the souls will migrate, mostly underground, and this is discussed below. Is this something bad? Well, I'd say the outcome is karma-relative.

If you're longing for salvation in the form of the 2nd coming (reincarnation) of Christ, don't get your hopes up. According to my theories and hypotheses, there have been numerous comings of Christ - this is the 33rd one and this is the 33rd time he was overwhelmed with disharmony (in about half of these incarnations he has been killed during or after transformation). The Christ cannot align your soul with the soul of god for you. If you have failed to do so the 1st time, you will probably fail to do so the 33rd time. Salvation is in your self renouncing the habit of serving the devil. That is, if you genuinely believe that is bad. Absolutely bad it is not. There's a slight probability that hell is actually a nice place, but even if it is not, you'll evolve and get used to the heat over time - think of the current global warming on the god's ectoderm as a training. Should you then oppose global warming, or accept it? Honestly, I think you'll get what you deserve either way some day. In any case, you'll live

in some way. I sometimes wonder myself - should I support the system (devil) so the end can be reached sooner, or should I continue on the path I am? Of course, the question for me is rhetorical, as it probably is for you. Per the theory of planetary neurogenesis, the current serving of the devil will be, most likely - through the application of karma, transformed into the serving of god. The difference between people like me and the general population is that I have transformed ahead (probably because I genuinely wanted to change). The other difference is that I do not want to serve anyone by force - neither the god nor the devil, nor do I want anyone to serve me by force. I am a universal musician, it is in my nature to create and seek universal harmony, just as it seeks and shapes me as its own instrument through the resonance of synchronicity. From this place, there are no bounds in space and time, one can see everything - love in devil's eye, hate in god's behind, seeds of modesty in rich, all the poor producing greed of plenty. I can also see myself descending into disharmony every time I fail to see the value in it. For the disharmony may not be in my nature, it may not be comfortable for me, but it is of equal value to the cosmos of reality.

As I wrote the words above, I decided to watch some motion picture, and right at the beginning of the movie, a quote from H. Miller is shown:

*"Every man has his own destiny:
the only imperative is to follow it,
to accept it, no matter where it leads him."*

So the god has spoken? But has the god matured, or is this a message of a growing child? To my god I say, my destiny is yours as your destiny is mine.

1.4 Rebirth

Some people experience transformation of consciousness at some point during life. After such transformation, even with no abrupt changes of the body (although changes definitely exist, mostly on epigenetic level), the person is effectively a new human being, hence, the term "rebirth" may be used to refer to the event.

I generally assume that people who experience rebirth are generally non-polarized people who have been expressing polarized behaviour before transformation, or, people of neutralum[4] species (even though they might express occasional polarized behaviour to some degree even after transformation).

Why the expression of polarized behaviour before transformation? I consider it as a natural process of development. If neutrality evolves from polarization, this is not surprising. We are all living through our past evolution (albeit in lossy compressed form) during development, from the conception to maturity. We all have tails, for example, at some point during embryonic stage. Long-term polarized behaviour, however, makes the neutralums unhappy.

However, transformation is possible in polarized species too and the term *rebirth* should probably be used whenever this transformation brings significant changes.

In polarized individuals this may be a transformation from dominant material to dominant spiritual intelligence or *vice versa*. In neutralum individuals this will be loss of expression of polarized behaviour (which was present initially in part due to polarized body ancestors, e.g., one of the parents).

1.5 Christ

By the theory of planetary neurogenesis, evolution of life on the surface of a planet is effectively coded so the cultivation of human or human-like species in neurogenesis events does not differ much between these events on different related planets. In fact, it is even possible that such species are cultivated in most, if not all, neurogenesis events on the same planet.

Equivalents of figures that significantly affect this cultivation should be present then in every such event. Therefore, the equivalent soul of the soul of Jesus Christ who lived recently on Earth should also exist in every event (whenever homo-like species are cultivated) and may be referred to as the soul of christ species.

1.6 Anti-christ

Traditionally, *antichrist* is a label used by the church of Christianity to refer to anyone who does not agree with the Trinity doctrine or doesn't accept Christianity. Likely, such antichrists have often been falsely accused to have something against Jesus Christ. A behaviour common for ideological fundamentalists.

Similar can be seen in today's politics in Europe, where [supposedly] democratic parties in power want to ban other parties (*you can choose who you're gonna vote for as long as you vote for us*) or cancel elections (*we choose us for you*) on the pretext of "saving democracy". It's an absurd and perverse behaviour, where people obviously do not practice what they preach and even accuse those who do practice what they themselves preach of *heresy*. The church and religious zealots do not

practice what Jesus preached so they would even call Jesus the antichrist if Jesus would be publicly preaching today.

Jesus Christ was against the government, while the church of Christianity was often working in collusion with government (when it wasn't government itself). It has used the figure of Christ and moulded it to fit its agenda. It is thus the church of Christianity who is a true antichrist in that sense.

Here, with a soul previously defined as a graviton[5], I define anti-christ as a soul which is the anti-particle of the soul of christ [species].

Assuming the christ and anti-christ souls are gravitons or graviton neutrinos, in particle physics these would be considered neutral particles. The christ particle could then be its own anti-particle. However, in my theories, souls evolve and I consider anti-christ to be a progressively evolved christ particle, which itself evolves from some more fundamental graviton. In fact, in my theories, no two particles can be absolutely the same and everything evolves over time, it is only due to inherent limitations of observers that differences may be unresolvable.

Both, embodied christ and, afterwards, anti-christ souls, should have been present on Mars during Mars' 6th event of neurogenesis and on Venus during Venus' 6th event of neurogenesis. The equivalents of the same may also be present during adult planetary neurogenesis events if human/human-like species are cultivated during such events.

Here it is assumed that the appearance of *christ* and *anti-christ* figures is coded in the evolution of life during neurogenesis. The same is true for all other figures that have significant influence on local evolution.

I hypothesize that this anti-christ is Moses or a precursor incarnation of Moses, and, likely, this is the *same* soul that incarnates in Jesus. Over evolution, Jesus then precedes Moses. I chose the name Moses for the anti-christ because I believe the figure may be highly correlated with the figure from the Bible, although the stories involving Moses in the Bible may refer to past events, preceding Jesus. With the collapse of civilization during the 6th major extinction, the unfolding events will probably resemble those in these stories. In addition, the predicted elevated synchronicity provides a reasonable explanation for *miracles*, or extraordinary phenomena and events present in the stories[6].

The *2nd coming* of the Christ is thus the coming of the Anti-christ. There are, however, two interpretations of this - either a single soul oscillates between

two species (in this case between christ and anti-christ) or a soul in complex organisms is generally a superposition of two particles one of which periodically becomes dominant (I generally choose this interpretation). For Jesus Christ and his subsequent incarnations I hypothesize two periods - up to the age of ≈ 36 the christ particle is dominant, afterwards the anti-christ dominates, up to the age of ≈ 85 . A person can die at the moment of transformation (mostly depending on the reaction of the environment) as Jesus did. However, in the *2nd coming*, he doesn't die and is transformed to anti-christ about the age of 36 (transformation is a rebirth event). There may be no much difference between christ and anti-christ souls, however, the christ *incarnation* is correlated with significantly higher expression of polarization, which can be correlated with polarized parents but may also be interpreted as a normal part of the anti-christ development.

Relatively, anti-christ *evolves* from a christ in each incarnation, however, the change may become permanent over time as the probability for neutral parents increases.

This individual obviously has some importance in the 6th major extinction (neurogenesis event) - most likely, his date of birth or rebirth can be used for calibration, to predict the dates of cataclysmic events of neurogenesis.

The Anti-christ could thus be interpreted as a marker or a messenger, informing people (or someone else) about the upcoming events, although it may have other roles as well. Considering the current state and hypothesized development of the 6th major extinction, this person should already be living on Earth.

1.6.1 On cataclysmic events

In the analysis of the Solar System, I have found the periods of the first three orders of oscillation of energy in the system to be: 4.25 billion years (1st order), 25.92 million years (2nd order) and 1.512 million years. These should be interpreted as average periods between strong cataclysmic events, with magnitude corresponding to order (1st order being most energetic).

Events of 4th and 5th order might produce significant effects, but they should be of lower magnitude and lower duration.

Due to oscillation and likely similarity between cataclysms (difference being in magnitude and duration, not much in effects), it is possible that Moses in the Bible can be correlated with a character that already existed on Earth (and survived a smaller *cataclysm*) before Jesus. However, in that case I'd interpret that character as a Moses precursor (or Moses *minor*), while the Moses I'm referring to in my works is the one associated with a major extinction (cataclysm), or Moses *major*, and that one comes after Christ.

Initially, I did not hypothesize on the periods of 4th and 5th order - they should be less than 100,000 years long though. If they are scaled relative to the 3rd order period as 3rd is to 2nd, 2nd is to 1st or 3rd is to 1st, possible period candidates are:

- 9221.4 years (4th order) and 537.9 years (5th order),

- 9221.4 years (4th order) and 56.2 years (5th order),
- 88200 years (4th order) and 5145 years (5th order),
- 88200 years (4th order) and 537.9 years (5th order).

The actual periods could be, however, closer to superpositions of these, possibly ≈ 44000 years (4th order) and ≈ 7200 years (5th order) on average.

Interestingly, 5th order period of 5145 years is in agreement with Hapgood's periodic catastrophic pole shifts while 7200 years is in agreement with Brown's periodic pole shifts (crustal displacement).

However, I am not convinced that strong global cataclysmic events occur with the beginning/end of a 4th or 5th order cycle. Sudden large pole shifts with these periods don't seem to be plausible, they are not predicted nor required for hypothesized planetary neurogenesis so they are not expected even with bigger cycles.

Events of the 4th order should produce significant large-scale effects though (the extinction of Neanderthals could be an such effect) and even 5th order cycles might leave a mark.

While pole shifts might not occur during these events, analysis of historic events and signs of past cataclysmic events on Earth's surface (e.g., effects of certain mega-tsunamis[7]) suggests crustal displacement may occur to some degree with 4th order events. Here, the spin momentum of Earth's crust would get temporarily decreased (the mechanism would likely be related to sudden changes in Earth's magnetic field, either directly - mf collapse polarizing the MOHO discontinuity, or, indirectly, changing the state of the medium from liquid to semi-liquid and vice-versa[8]). Due to lack of friction and lacking polarization, troposphere and oceans would not change momentum significantly, which would then result in extreme winds blowing over land (at supersonic speeds if crust slows down significantly) and oceans flooding the land. Changing momenta would, obviously, also cause earthquakes and volcanism.

One sign of tsunamis/mega-tsunamis are wedge-shaped sediment deposits, called chevrons. Interestingly, a lot of chevrons can be found about the coastlines of the world, and some extend deep into the interior. Conventional assumption is that most of these have been created slowly by winds, as they are commonly aligned with the prevailing wind direction. In some cases of chevrons, some do hypothesize the origin in mega-tsunamis caused by asteroid/cometary impacts. However, given the lack of solid evidence for the associated impacts, and considering the fact that the winds/tsunamis produced with crustal displacement would be exactly aligned with normal prevailing winds (in fact, the winds would be the same prevailing winds, *only* significantly amplified), it is possible that some of these chevrons are the effect of cataclysmic crustal displacement instead.

While these events could certainly be cataclysmic, I'd refer to them as weak cataclysms (at least if they are of the 4th order) - albeit violent, these are short-lived excursions not affecting all parts of the world equally and may not be so evident in fossil records.

It is possible that even weaker cataclysms occur at the end of 5th order periods (assuming these periods last at least a couple of centuries), however, if these periods are less than a couple of millennia long, effect on crust momentum is likely negligible. In that case, catastrophic events on surface could be induced by energy propagating vertically from strong deep-focus earthquakes (effect on MOHO might itself be partial).

Indeed, this could be what caused the volcanic winter of 536 AD (or, "a dark hour in Dark Ages").

Interestingly, assuming something [weakly] cataclysmic also happened about 0 AD, this would agree with the calculated 5th order period of about 537.9 years.

As I have hypothesized elsewhere[9], Jesus was experiencing *heavy* synchronicity during his life (mostly at the end). It would not be surprising then that his birth (or death) was synchronized with the start of a 5th order cycle.

Of course, the period of 537.9 years is the average (mean) - 5th order periods can generally be shorter and longer than that, but generally not more than a couple of decades.

The same is true for 4th order periods, which could however deviate by 100-1000 years.

Additional analysis of magnetic excursions and supervolcanic eruptions reveals that the best fit would then be the first proposed combination, of 9221.4 years for the 4th order period and 537.9 years for the 5th order, as shown in Table 1 for the last 9 cycles. The agreement is remarkable with hypothesized

cycle	years before present	associated event
0	~0	current events (extinction, magnetic excursion or reversal, ...)
1	9221.4	¹⁰ Be enrichment in ice cores ≈9200 years ago[10] (hypothesized extreme solar storm event), Lake Michigan/Erie magnetic excursion 10-9 ka and 14-12 ka[11]
2	18442.8	Hilina Pali magnetic excursion 18.5 ka[12]
3	27664.2	Lake Mungo magnetic excursion 30780±520 - 28140±370 and ≈26000 years b.p.[13], Oruanui eruption ≈26.5 ka[14]
4	36885.6	Mono Lake magnetic excursion 36 - 30 ka[15] (34.5 ka[12]), Dome C/Vostok ¹⁰ Be enrichment (likely due to excursion) ≈35 ka[16]
5	46107.0	Laschamp magnetic excursion 46.6±2.4 ka[17] (41.2 ka[12]), Neanderthals extinction
6	55328.4	?
7	64549.8	Norwegian-Greenland Sea magnetic excursion 64.5 ka[12]
8	73771.2	Toba volcanic eruption ≈74000 years ago[18]

Table 1: 4th order period correlation with excursions

associated events, however, if the proper date for Laschamp is 41.2 ka and assuming Gothenburg magnetic excursion (13.75 - 12.35 ka[19]) is also a part of this cycling, it is possible that the 4th order period of 9221.4 years occasionally breaks into (or is composed of) two, perhaps equal, periods - which would also

explain the 14-12 ka Lake Michigan/Erie excursion.

The existence of a 3rd harmonic is also possible - as it could be correlated with the Noah's Great Flood (dated to ≈ 6000 years by Biblical scholars), giving a date about 6148 years ago.

The same harmonic could also be correlated with the recent rapid shrinkage of human brains (dated to ≈ 3000 years ago[20]), giving a date some 3074 years ago.

The 2nd harmonic (1536.9 y) of that harmonic (or, 6th harmonic of the 4th order period) could be correlated with Dansgaard-Oeschger warm events (for which some hypothesize a ~ 1470 year period[21]).

Interestingly, assuming the 5th order period is 537.9 years, with the same scaling, the 6th order period would be 31-32 years (on average). This is in good agreement with the lifespan of Jesus but may be more correlated with events happening in or about the year 0 AD and year 33 AD (I believe Jesus was born in year 5 BC, he died in 33 AD).

Since beginnings/ends of 5th order periods should be relatively synchronized with beginnings/ends of 6th order periods, this further corroborates the hypothesis that Jesus's birth was synchronized with the start of a 5th order period.

This then confirms the above hypothesis that some humans are markers of change or messengers of cataclysmic events. Jesus was announcing apocalypse but he was delusional about the time of occurrence (he convinced himself that the apocalypse will occur about the time of his death).

The birth, rebirth or death of the Anti-christ (Moses) should not only be relatively synchronized with a 5th order cycle, but with a 4th, 3rd and at least 2nd too (if we are indeed in the middle of a major extinction) - since the 1st cycle period is 4.25 billion years (equal to hypothesized age of body of Earth), there's strong possibility he is synchronized with a 1st order cycle too.

The conventionally accepted age of Earth is 4.54 billion years. However, this estimate is based on the assumption of absolute constancy of decay rates of elements. Absolute constancy is impossible according to CR and I have theorized not only periodic oscillation, but also strong temporary deviation from mean values during strong events. Based on this, a proper (real) age of Earth has been calculated to be roughly 4.25 billion years, equal to the 1st order period. However, as the value for the 1st order period represents an average value, the end of the 1st order cycle may be some time in the future (e.g., about 26 million years away).

Since lifespan of Moses is much longer than 31-32 years (average duration of the 6th order period) and he should be of neutralum species, he must live through a rebirth (transformation of consciousness, or soul transformation) in his thirties.

I hypothesize that the rebirth of Moses marks the point of no return (the start of the apocalypse), while his death marks the end of the planet's neurogenesis

event. —————

2 Introduction

While Mars, having significantly lower mass, might not belong to the same species of life as Earth, it should belong to the same class of life (e.g., *mammalia*) and there shouldn't be any large difference in embryogenesis and neurogenesis apart from scale and rate of evolution - same species of cells/proteins should be involved (evolved), with the main difference being in the volume/mass of organs (e.g., brain layers) and in the ratio between proteins of different species.

Unlike Earth, Mars and Venus should be fully developed planets and last neurogenesis occurred on any of these might have been adult neurogenesis (assuming these do occur on surface), rather than embryonic.

All complex life on the surface of a planet such as Earth, existing during Phanerozoic, represent progenitor neural proteins and cells, which, after maturation, transform and migrate to neural tube equivalents during major *extinction* events, from where they differentiate and migrate to mantle layers.

According to my theories and research, such major (and likely final embryonic) event should occur this century on Earth, and here I will discuss details of that, 6th major, *extinction* event, in some prophecies commonly referred to as the *Judgement day*.

Inverse reference to (or correlation with) the 6th major extinction is present in The Revelation, chapter 6, seal nr. 6:

"I pogledah kada on otvori šesti pečat, i gle, nastade velik potres;"

Strong earthquakes should be common phenomena during major extinctions, including the 6th major extinction.

"i postade sunce crno kao gruba tkanina od dlake, a mjesec postade kao krv;"

Temporary collapse of at least one of the Sun's large scale gravitons is expected during the major extinctions, this could significantly decrease amount of radiation reaching Earth and Moon, so the Moon may glow red. The Moon may also glow red for a while due to volcanism induced with the expansion of its own gravitational maximum (soul delocalization).

"i zvijezde s neba padoše na zemlju kao što smokva odbacuje svoje nezrele plodove kada je potrese silan vjetar."

Asteroid bombardment is also expected during these extinctions. These are relative triggers of local energy level changes of large scale gravitons. While the magnitude of bombardment should be decreasing with each extinction due to decreasing energy requirements, large asteroids should not be excluded even during the 6th major extinction.

"I iščeznu nebo kao svitak knjige kada se smota, i svaka planina i otok bijahu maknuti sa svojih mjesta."

If the predicted collapse and recession of Earth's magnetic field precedes collapse of the Sun, significant amount of atmosphere will be stripped from Earth.

The displacement of land, incl. mountains and isles, is expected during the process of Earth's mantle gyrification.

"A zemaljski kraljevi, i velikaši, i bogataši, i vojskovođe, i moćnici, i svaki rob, i svaki slobodnjak, sakriše se u špilje i među gorske stijene;"

Cataclysmic changes will affect everyone and effectively erase inequality between people. Hiding in mountain caves is also consistent with hypothesized global flooding of lowlands.

"i rekoše gorama i stijenama: Padnite na nas i sakrijte nas od lica onoga koji sjedi na prijestolju i od Jaganjčeve srdžbe: jer došao je veliki dan njegova gnjeva i tko će opstati?"

The final acceptance of punishment of β .cancerous for its sins, probably due to fear and lack of choice.

Instead of using the conventionally adopted term *homo sapiens*, I refer to the extant polarized homo species as homo.beta or beta.cancerous, as there is clearly nothing *sapientis* (wise) in the behaviour of the polarized modern society, although unwise can be a precursor to (a *beta* version of) wise. Different subspecies of humans, however, exist, and some are a bit wiser, something explored in another work[4].

If we agree on the following:

- we are in the middle of the 6th major extinction,
- the point of no return has been reached or should be reached this century,

- apocalypse described in the Bible refers to this extinction (which was *confirmed* by Newton who calculated the Day of Judgement should be in the period 2060-2344[22], but later revised this to 2016-2344),

then we might ask how is that prediction possible. And there are several possibilities:

- this is a complete coincidence (as would probably be a common answer in delusional mainstream reductionism),
- this is an event of synchronicity, meaningful and relative coincidence,
- the predictive power of Bible has a source in some 3rd party intelligence [familiar with neurogenesis] that has somehow influenced the authors of the Bible or the prophets,

Well, according to my theories, causality is relative and future is relatively coded (that does not mean it cannot be changed, this is the equivalent of genetic coding so the probability for change may be low but it exists). Major extinctions (apocalypses) are part of hypothesized neurogenesis events so they must be coded somewhere and it should not be surprising that a rough date of one such event can be extrapolated or predicted (with precision improving as the extinction becomes nearer). I will not discuss here how precisely this date (period) ended up in the Bible but, along with the description of upcoming apocalyptic events, I consider it very accurate.

I also find the original Egyptian/Sumerian religion and *their* large structures very intriguing. I am convinced some interesting things are also encoded there and here this too will be explored.

3 Definition

The speed of photons and gravitational waves on standard scale (U_0) is 2.99792458×10^8 m/s. We experience these waves on regular basis.

Such waves on the scale of U_1 particles (e.g., Solar System) travel at the speed of 2.93×10^6 m/s (this speed was hypothesized in CR[2] and proved in the Solar System analysis[1]). Unless locally absorbed/emitted, these waves don't noticeably affect Earth. However, due to local entanglements, local changes in energy levels of large scale gravitons will be relatively synchronized so local emissions will involve local absorptions as well. On this scale of energies, it can take millions of years between highly energetic disruptions (changes in energy levels) of the Solar System.

More frequent smaller disturbances (e.g., as a consequence of specific entanglement with external systems) cannot be excluded. Indeed, I have previously found that the entanglement (resonance) of the Solar System with the Sirius System could be producing smaller periodic disturbances

on the order of millennia[23].

I have previously predicted such changes on a periodic basis - 1.512 million years, 25.74 - 25.92 million years and 4.25×10^9 years[1]. These are pulses of strong evolution - temporarily disrupting decay rates, effectively compressing timescales, all correlated with rapid evolution of some species and extinction of others.

The largest (major) events of these, at least, have an additional component - transmigration.

A Judgement day is, thus, a *day* when the surface life differentiates into various parts (*proteins* and *cells*) of homo. Ω [4] (Earth in this case) neural components, and is transferred to appropriate location within its [brain] mantle. With 5 major extinctions (correlated with neurogenesis events) behind us, the current event is the Judgement Day 6.

Here, the target layer of the mantle depends on the polarization of individual's soul (and it's associated space). I find the name (Judgement day) appropriate as this polarization reflects the nature of the soul's intelligence and I assume life gets harder with mantle depth. The length of this *day* is however relative and it has 2 interpretations - it may be interpreted as the length of a day in life of Earth (god) or a day in human life.

In case of Earth's *day*, it would last from the beginning of the first to the end of the last wave of the 6th stage of neurogenesis (*extinction* pulses can be divided into multiple energy levels - waves), possibly spanning <100 years. In the other interpretation, defining it as the time of actual migration (which is preceded by differentiation), it refers to the day when the migration starts - although once started, the migration to the interior itself probably lasts just a couple of days.

Duration of migration can be inferred from brain *rinse* cycles, which are cycles of exchange of blood and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) in the brain. In case of planets like Earth, cerebrospinal fluid is a salty ocean water while blood is generally magma.

If scaled up from the *rinse* cycle of a human brain which lasts 20s[24], the transfer on Earth lasts 7 days:

$$\frac{T}{T_{x_h}} T_x = \frac{20 s}{50 y} 1512000 y = 604800 s = 7 \text{ days}$$

where T is the period of human *rinse* cycle, T_x is the period between strong evolution pulses on Earth of the 3rd order (general oscillation) and T_{x_h} is T_x on human scale, which is equal to the average human lifespan over the course of evolution.

Note that T_x is much shorter than the age of the Earth's body of matter.

Even though I believe the same body of Earth is reused between incarnations, this period might not represent the average lifetime of Earth's soul (large scale graviton) in Earth's body, rather a temporary loss of consciousness. However, during hypothesized embryogenic neurogenesis, this is the effective average lifetime.

Note that the period of 7 days is equal to the rotation period of the Sun's core, which should temporarily collapse with every 2nd order cycle (which should also be synchronized with the collapse of the one of Earth's large scale gravitons).

If one interprets the Judgement day as a day in Earth's [3rd order] life cycle, this *day* lasts:

$$J = \frac{1}{T_{x_h} \times 365.25 y^{-1}} T_x = \frac{1}{50 y \times 365.25 y^{-1}} 1512000 y = 82.8 \text{ years}$$

However, it is probably more appropriate to use a 360-day year in calculation (superposition of solar and lunar year, commonly used in prophecies as well), which gives:

$$J = \frac{1}{T_{x_h} \times 360 y^{-1}} T_x = \frac{1}{50 y \times 360 y^{-1}} 1512000 y = 84 \text{ years}$$

Note that my most likely lifetime in the current incarnation, and the most likely lifetime of the Anti-christ, is 85 ± 2 years[25].

Using the obtained Anti-christ lifetime[25] as T_{x_h} instead (assuming it is equal to 84 years - the obtained value, as noted above, is 85 ± 2 y), the *day* would last:

$$J_m = \frac{1}{84 y \times 360 y^{-1}} 1512000 y = 50 \text{ years}$$

Interestingly, the ratio 84/50 is very close to the golden or divine ratio. Assuming the ratio should be equal to the golden ratio, with 84 years for T_{x_h} , one obtains 52.533 years for J_m .

There are two possible years which may be considered as the start of the Judgement Day, year of the Anti-christ's birth (1981) and year of its soul *rebirth*

or the *anti-christ* birth (2017±1)[25] - as noted before, prior to transformation the soul of an anti-christ is a christ soul.

This gives, for the end of the Judgement *Day*:

$$1981 + 84 = 2065$$

$$2017 + 50 = 2067$$

Taking into account rebirth uncertainty, this gives a superposition 2066±2.

Other possible years are 2031 (1981+50), 2101 (2017+84), 2063.8 (1981+82.8), 2099.8 (2017+82.8) and, out of these, years 2031 and 2063 may have some significance (years 2101 and 2099 probably imply the Anti-christ would have to live to the age of 119±1 which is probably unlikely). Year 2031 is also unlikely for the end, but it may be an important year (at least for the Anti-christ and/or myself) as I have previously hypothesized another change in my soul's energy level at that time. There is some possibility for my own death at that time but in that case I will probably reincarnate on the surface again and live for about 36 years. Obviously, according to my hypothesis on Christ reincarnation[25], the birth/transformation/death of the Anti-christ is aligned with my own birth/transformation/death. One can interpret this as a coincidence or not, but I do not consider the identity of the Anti-christ as something important - only the dates associated with his birth, transformation and death. Thus, I do not claim I am the anti-christ of the 6th Judgement day on Earth, but whoever it is, I believe the person should be living on Earth already and the above calculations should not be far off. With that said, however, there are quite interesting signals suggesting that I am the guy[26].

This is also in agreement with my previous calculations - year 2066 is one of the predicted *impact* years[27]. The last wave of migration may thus end about the year 2066 (ending human presence on the planet's surface), with surface closure then probably ending about 2084.

On the *point of no return*

Correlation of birth and *rebirth* of an anti-christ with the 6th major extinction may not satisfy certain people. On its own, it wouldn't satisfy me either as a signal of the end, but there are other signals.

Year 2017±1 was certainly the *point of no return* for me, but this point was not far off for the world too (up to the *point of no return* it may have been possible to delay the extinction, perhaps 1.5 million or even

≈26 million years in time).

Others too have recognized that year as different[28] or a major turning point for the world[29].

Among other peculiar phenomena, this was a year when D. Trump was elected as US president. It was also the year when birth rate in China started decreasing sharply - even though two-child policy was implemented at the same time (up to that point one-child policy was in effect).

These two countries have the largest impact on the world. Trump may have done a lot of damage to Earth, but this sharp birth rate decrease in China, despite the implementation of two-child policy, is particularly interesting because, obviously, the cultivation of progenitor neural cells must reach a peak eventually (note that migration is synchronized with this peak) and a decrease in fertility is a strong signal that the peak is near.

The fertility rate did not change significantly, but the number of males and females aged 15 - 49 (generally fertile population) is decreasing sharply. The gap between males and females in this group is also increasing, female population is decreasing at a faster rate than male population - this fact, along with global decrease in fertility, is a strong signal of the imminent end of cultivation of homo on Earth's surface.

Interestingly, in year 2016 globally averaged temperatures reached 1°C above the mid-20th century mean and up to this point this is still the anomaly maximum (it was reached again in 2020, but not surpassed). Note that this is not only the maximum of recent history, but a maximum for the last ≈12000 years. Note that there might exist some additional uncertainty in these years, if the start of the Judgement Day occurs at one of the predicted *impact* years (which are correlated with atmospheric CO₂), then year 2015 is a better candidate (when yearly average atmospheric CO₂ levels have reached 400 ppm).

However, another strong signal that the year 2016 was the point of no return comes from Newton. Deciphering Bible, that is one of the two possible years he calculated to bring the end of the world [as we know it]. In fact, Newton stated that the Day of Judgement cannot come before year 2060 and after 2344. Year 2060 was later revised to 2016. However, Newton also said "It is not for us to know the times and seasons which God has put in his own breast.". This statement is important (originally it also comes from the Bible) and it signals that the *Day of Judgement* is a longer period and we will not even know when the Judgement Day has started. In my interpretation, either year 2060 or 2016 should be interpreted as the point of no return, a point which we will pass without noticing anything highly extraordinary - continuing our business as usual. This is how it has to be for neurogenesis to proceed as coded. There are a lot of tipping points associated with climate, however, I believe the most

important tipping point, regarding sustainability of life, is one concerning biodiversity loss[30]. In 2016, global wildlife populations have decreased by 66% since 1970.[31].

Another strong signal are the analyses done by J. Bendell, who argues that global societal collapse started about the year 2016[32] (it is probably more appropriate to say that the start was centred in year 2016, but spread globally from 2014 to 2018, with multiple factors included).

Something else very important happened in 2016 - it appears to have been a turning point for Antarctic sea ice. Up to 2016 the sea ice extent has actually been rising steadily since the beginning of measurements. But in 2016 the sea ice extent plummeted and hasn't recovered ever since. In fact, measured record anomalous decline[33] in 2023 is a very convincing signal that this is a new trend and there won't be any recovery. Unexpected spikes of methane in 2020/2021 and stratospheric water vapour injection with the Hunga Tonga eruption in 2022[34] do suggest humans have lost control of the climate (if they ever had any). And even if reversal may be theoretically possible, when mentality of the human race (e.g., optimization for short-term profit or profiteering) is taken into account, the *point of no return* is likely behind us. But does it make sense to talk about the *point of no return* at all? If it is coded we were effectively destined to pass it - probability for us not to pass it was *infinitesimal* in the first place.

Both interpretations of the Judgement Day length could be considered correct - the *day* in the first interpretation (50-84 years in length) ending with the *day* in the other interpretation (7 human days in length).

4 Tornado of souls

Below is my vision of neurogenesis in homo. Ω individuals (planets), more specifically, its last stage, as it will be happening on Earth. Although I do not doubt neurogenesis and transmigration of life, there are multiple possibilities and it is hard to know the details, so the actual mechanics behind the process may be somewhat different than described here. Also, my description involves collapses or large scale gravitons (gravitational maxima) which are hypothesized to exist in CR[2] (and for which evidence is provided in other papers), but alternative routes may be possible.

Embryonic development of individuals in general represents a lossy-compressed evolution of the species the individual belongs to. How compressed and how lossy the process is depends how much the species are evolved. Human neocortex, for example, didn't always have 10 billion neurons. There were periods of weak evolution - when the number of neurons was kept relatively constant, and strong evolution - when the number of neurons was significantly and rapidly

increased. The evolution takes a lot of time so it occurs over many different incarnations of the soul. In case of animals in which the body is discarded after each incarnation, this implies many different bodies, and with every birth past incarnations are re-evolved in compressed form. Thus, in such animals, every new gestation period associated with a particular soul implies a new body. Development of a planet like Earth, however, is much less compressed and since there is no conventional reproduction, the same body is reused with different incarnations of the soul (even different souls may be involved). Thus, the planet, during its development, experiences multiple gestation periods. A planet like Earth does not experience a single embryonic neurogenesis event, rather 6 of them.

A process equivalent to gestation in humans on Earth begins about 12000 years before the cultivation of neural progenitors in a neurogenesis event reaches its peak and the migration starts. It will be shown later that in the current neurogenesis event the gestation started with the start of Holocene (exactly the time when humans started building progenitor cells). The prominent neural progenitor mass in the current event are obviously humans and human population is likely to peak this century. So what exactly happens once the peak is reached? Migration towards the south pole is stimulated (with a possible temporary precursor migration towards the north). Stimulation mechanisms may be diverse, generally, however, the south pole should be increasing habitability while the habitability elsewhere is decreasing, and migration may start even before the peak. Since we are at the end of a 3rd order cycle, the peak is probably relatively synchronized with a temporary collapse of the Sun's outer large scale graviton (gravitational maximum) (this involves a change in spin momentum and may be externally stimulated), resulting in ejection of plasma (this includes highly energetic electrons, protons and atomic nuclei up to Fe), as during these times the radial thermal momentum of plasma should overcome the gravitational attraction. This happens on average every 1.512 million years and is assumed to be a temporary transition to a lower local energy level - towards the core radius. The single transition interval should not exceed 2.97 minutes, giving 5.94 minutes total (the exact interval depends on the nature of graviton tunnelling in the process, but, in any case, gravitational coupling should be significantly reduced during the time so the transition probably doesn't last longer than that). The ejection of plasma should happen within that interval. However, the collapsed state may last longer - from 1 to 4 weeks.

As gravitational changes propagate at the speed of light, some 8.31666 minutes after the collapse the small (standard) scale gravitational/electro-magnetic waves should arrive to Earth. These should not have a big impact on Earth (the ejected plasma following these waves will, however, probably have a big impact on human technology). However, large scale energy levels in the Sun are discrete and at least one of these is entangled with Earth. Thus, one large scale wave is likely to be absorbed by Earth. As these travel at 2.93×10^6 m/s, it should take about 14.18 hours for this wave to arrive. The effect will depend on energy, but this should be relatively synchronized with the collapse of the Earth's magnetic field (due to changes in spin momenta of large scale gravitons,

associated with energy level changes) and the asteroid bombardment.

During weak evolution, chances for asteroid bombardment are low, however, during strong evolution, large gravitational disturbances are hypothesized to occur, when the chances are significantly increased. Not only that, a mechanism (correlated with graviton expansion/contraction) is proposed that could induce the bombardment, nudging the asteroids towards the planet. This is explained in the analysis of the Solar System[35].

If this is the last neurogenesis event, it should also be synchronized with the collapse/expansion of the Moon's large scale graviton. Depending on graviton energy, this may result in the splitting of the Moon into two, now dead, bodies. This graviton should then be absorbed by Earth.

The two moons of Mars, Phobos and Deimos, are likely the remains of a single moon split during this process on Mars. In that case, they should be similar in composition, have equal inclination (relative to Mars' equator) and axial tilt. Indeed, they do have equal inclination ($\approx 1^\circ$), axial tilt (0°)[36] and they apparently are of similar composition[37].

In this process, the artificial satellites orbiting Earth could become projectiles, as many would be accelerated towards the Earth.

Collapse of [one of] the Earth's large scale graviton[s] (transition to a higher energy level) should also be synchronized with the expulsion of energy towards the mantle. If this is synchronized with a large asteroid impact, the expulsion of energy should be directional, concentrating on the antipodal location.

This energy is likely to be in the form of mantle plumes, however, it would probably be more appropriate to refer to synchronicity rather than use cause-effect relationships, as causality is hypothesized to be very relative here. Therefore, the build-up of mantle plumes could precede the collapse, even for millions of years if that is necessary. Similar is valid for other correlated events, wherever the cause-effect relationships are used here one should consider them very relative. These processes (e.g., magma movement) are not linear, however, and should be accelerated near to, and with, the collapse.

This should then be relatively synchronized with increasing frequency of earthquakes, volcanism and flooding.

Changes in local gravitational pressure will affect hypothesized primary neutrinos bound to standard atoms, which will disrupt decay rates of elements, temporarily accelerating them (again, with relative causality, this may be already happening).

With changes in gravitational and electro-magnetic potential, Earth's surface may temporarily expand, and the atmosphere may even temporarily invert (including a part of hydrosphere).

The Earth's magnetic field will recede inwards and the global magnetic dipole will disappear from the surface. Assuming this is the final embryonic neurogenesis event, the global magnetic dipole won't be restored on Earth's surface after the event.

The moons (those with a distinct gravitational maximum) of a planet (and planets to star) generally indicate polarization, and the strength of a magnetic field of a host body in such system is likely to be proportional to the number of its moon *charges*.

It is assumed that the moon collapse occurs only with the final event of neurogenesis, however, this is questionable. If untrue, the Earth may have had multiple moons in its history. If the current Earth-Moon system is a scaled Sun-Mars system (as Moon's orbit relative to Earth suggests - being scaled Mars' orbit relative to the Sun), it appears there should have been exactly 3 more moons at appropriate orbitals - *Mercury* moon (1 polarized large scale graviton), *Venus* moon (1 polarized graviton) and the *Earth* moon (3 gravitons).

However, depending on mass, fusion of orbitals (moons) may be possible (analysis of fossil records could reveal constraints on the number of moons and their masses). In another interpretation, thus, a single moon may be involved, one that is losing energy (gravitons) with each event - note that this implies loss of internal energy and subsequent surface healing at the exit point, with the mass symmetrically absorbed by Earth.

Tectonic plates may represent a result of mantle breaking due to expansion and moon graviton absorption. However, first expansion might not be associated with neurogenesis but with the creation of mantle/core discontinuity which occurred few billion years ago.

In case of the outer Solar System the gaseous planets take the role of the Sun while their moons form and develop similarly to terrestrial (inner) planets.

Due to extreme pressure exerted on the troposphere during collapse, it will compress and may partly liquefy and solidify.

Heavy ejecta from the Sun, such as iron nuclei, may then cover the compressed troposphere - the new (*imaginary*) surface of the Earth.

The *dust* absorption will not be homogeneous (partially due to magnetic fields involved) and concentration at the poles could be negligible.

The Fe oxides covering the surface of Mars may be the best evidence for this. Instead of meteoritic origin, most of surface iron may have been released from the Sun during collapses and reacted with oxygen from the frozen (and at times melting) troposphere, forming rust.

Hadn't this been the final stage in Mars' formation, it would still have a complete moon, a continuously present global magnetic field dipole and breathable atmosphere.

The deposits of ejecta on planets will depend on whether the local magnetic field is present. Mars' global magnetic dipole has been missing for a long time now, and if the Sun indeed periodically ejects heavy particles, these would accumulate on Mars (even if *complete* wave absorption does not occur locally).

If Martian troposphere has compressed, partially solidified and was covered with iron afterwards, areas on Mars could have thick layers of CO₂/water ice (not limited to the poles), covered with oxidized iron, significantly more at the equatorial region.

In another paper, I have predicted that the layer of ice should have an average thickness of 1500 m[38], all this has been recently confirmed - a massive layer of ice, 1500 m thick on average, covered with dust, in the equatorial region[39]. Dust deposits on ice are 300-600 m thick, how plausible is that it all came from meteorites?

If, in the process, collapsing Moon's graviton is converging to a ring-like form (if it wasn't already in such form), noticeable long-lived scars on the crust may be formed (as gravitational decoupling is not instant).

Note also that the Moon's maximum or large scale graviton can be a superposition of multiple quanta. If these are in a two-dimensional ring form during collapse, the recession should create linear rifts on the surface of the planet roughly parallel to equator (perpendicular to magnetic dipole axis), at or near the equator, and with a diameter somewhat larger than the diameter of the graviton. The rift would likely cause eruptions of magma on the surface before it is healed.

On Mars, Valles Marineris could be one evidence of this. It is a 4000 km long system of canyons with a straight rift ≈ 2000 km long, parallel to, and near the, equator.

The rift indicates that the diameter of the absorbed moon graviton was roughly half of Earth's moon (or Mars's core) diameter. Apparently, on Mars, the maximum has also been fragmented into 3 quanta, each 1/3 or possibly 1/2 of the next larger quantum.

Figure 1: Rifts on Mars, possibly created by its last absorbed moon maximum⁴⁰

This is shown in Fig. 1. As expected, the rifts are almost perfectly straight (usually the shape should not be preserved due to tectonic activity of a planet, however, tectonic activity should cease with the last neurogenesis event, so the scar can remain fossilized).

It is also apparent that Valles Marineris was once filled with out-flowing liquid - as predicted, this should have been lava, although it may have been filled with water too some time later. It would thus be interesting to analyse and date the basalt in Valles Marineris.

The fragmentation into 3 quanta is probably a consequence of the composite nature of the graviton and some temporal separation may exist between the absorption of each graviton. On Earth, assuming this is the last neurogenesis event and that it conforms to the model of the 21st century apocalypse, first rift may be created in the period 2029 - 2040, second in 2048 - 2055 and the last in 2061 - 2066, however this is questionable.

When polarized, gravitational maximum may have low gravity but strong electro-magnetic potential. Its polarized space also has a large spin momentum (highest at the maximum). As such, it will absorb and concentrate plasma about the maximum (oscillating between the poles). However, if superposition of gravitons is involved (or oscillation of a single graviton), multiple maxima will exist at different radii. If associated magnetic fields are anti-aligned the plasma could be concentrating inside the outer maximum and near the centre. This is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Plasma trapped between outer and inner gravitational maxima

Both, plasma and the ring are at high temperature and any contact with neutral matter will cause melting and vaporization. The bulge, or concentrated mass, could be low at the start of recession.

The recession will not only cause melting but redistribution of mass and may induce explosions in pressurized zones. With significant energy this will lead to ground collapse on one place and elevation/fracturing of ground on the other.

All these features are present on Mars, as shown in Fig. 3 (arrows indicate, from left to right: ground elevation/fracture, central bulge imprint and possible ground collapse), and can be associated with creation of Valles Marineris. The whole valley complex on the right and Tharsis region on the left have likely been created during the same event. These suggest that the maximum was moving to the left as it was descending into Mars (rotating relative to south pole).

Figure 3: Valles Marineris and nearby ground, image source: USGS⁴¹

The recession of a moon maximum is coupled with the recession of a global magnetic dipole of the planet and the two magnetic fields should be aligning at the time of recession. Rotation is thus not surprising.

While a rough dipole orientation at the time of entrance will remain fossilized in the rift orientation, the magnetic field itself is unlikely to fossilize in rocks formed in the event, due to recession.

On Mars, apparently, the angle of the maximum dipole at the time of entrance was $\sim 15^\circ$ from the geographic north-south, however, its rotation suggests Mars' dipole was aligning with the geographic north and south.

But Mars is not the only body in the Solar System scarred by gravitational maxima (assuming this is the correct interpretation). Saturn's moon Iapetus has a 1300 km long equatorial ridge, and, interestingly, also has sections with 3 near parallel ridges[42]. Like rifts on Mars, this is very hard to explain with common theories on planetary formation and development but easy with collapsing gravitational maxima. Creation of ridges on Iapetus, instead of rifts, suggests these were created as the soul (graviton) was exiting the body.

Note, however, that I do not favour the above interpretation for at least some parts of Mars' Tharsis region. I believe that at least the Syria Planum area (including Noctis Labyrinthus) has been created differently, as described in another paper[43].

It is questionable to what degree is planetary neurogenesis equivalent to standard neurogenesis in terms of complexity. In what form does life migrate? Are the large scale protein equivalents (e.g., humans) migrating inside cell equivalents or not, and are they migrating as living individuals, as DNA, or is the migration limited to souls (small scale gravitons)?

Humans are living in houses, which probably should be interpreted as neuron cell progenitors. Lately, people are even starting to use mycelium to build houses, with a tendency towards the use of living fungi. This has many benefits (allows, for example, for the house to heal itself) and houses in the future could indeed become living cells. Coupled with environmental changes and increasing virtualization of life, an increasing tendency exists towards physical confinement of people within these cells. Still, this does not imply migration will include cells, or transfer of living individuals. What is the role of the major mass extinction in this event? Environmental pressure generally stimulates migration in animals. In a neurogenesis event, induced environmental pressure probably will stimulate migration of humans south, and eventually to Antarctica (as I have explained in the analysis of the Solar System). Once there, they will settle underground in lava tubes - probably due to the collapsed magnetic field. There, they will be eventually stimulated or forced to migrate deeper inside Earth. This is why Antarctica is increasing habitability.

Are the lava tubes equivalents of neural tubes? Probably, if not they probably represent entrance tunnels to the neural tubes. In standard embryonic neurogenesis, two different ways are used to create neural tubes: primary - where the tube is formed with the subduction of the neural plate (part of the ectoderm), and secondary - where the tube forms by hollowing out of the solid interior precursor. Here, the equivalent primary process may be the subduction of oceanic plates (alternative is the creation of large deep rifts which eventually

close at the top), while the creation of lava tubes is equivalent to secondary neurulation. Primary and secondary tubes eventually connect to form a single tube[44].

I have also discussed previously[1] the creation of tunnels and how existence of multiple gravitational maxima inside Earth enables for habitable zones to exist deeper in the mantle of a planet, so this won't be discussed here.

Note that a large reservoir of magma does exist beneath Antarctica. Lava tubes will be created with the expulsion of this magma, probably correlated with an large asteroid impact at the antipodal location. Note that, unless the time gets significantly compressed with gravitational disturbances (which is, however, hypothesized to be happening), this impact must have had happened a few to ten million years ago in order for magma to reach the surface at this time (note also, however, that even if the impact had happened so long ago, this does not exclude local time compression and acceleration of the process). The south pole volcanism should also have a limited precursor in global volcanism sourced in other reservoirs (including earthquakes induced by magma intrusions). Increased and simultaneous seismic/magmatic activity from multiple usually active hotspots is likely but also from previously dormant or unusual places. The activation of hotspots should probably proceed from north to south, possibly even in a relatively straight or curved line if this is correlated with primary neurulation (e.g., from Iceland through Campi Flegrei, Santorini, towards the East African Rift, etc.), however, the actual surface emergence will depend on local conditions. Some of this could produce large effects, however, the lava (flood basalt) that will flow from Antarctica is the main volcanic event and should probably cover a good part of the planet (on Mars, it seems to have covered half of the surface, explaining its dichotomy).

I don't believe humans will migrate to Antarctica inside cells (unless some kind of flying cells are involved, and perhaps *some* 3rd party operating them), but cells could be used in migration to deep Earth. If so, these will be created in Antarctica. If this will be a migration of living individuals, how many will survive and migrate? Some form of *natural selection* may be involved.

However, unless travelling inside cells, the migration of living individuals is probably unlikely. In that case, a migration of genomes may be more plausible.

Note that a genome represents a single gene on this scale. So this would be a migration of large scale genes.

Changes in gravitational/electro-magnetic pressure may induce strong cyclones (initially possibly inverted - relative to Earth) fragmenting the atmosphere into individual cells which will gravitate towards the south pole (similar to the partial fragmentation of Jupiter's atmosphere currently localized to its poles).

Note that absorption of large scale gravitons does not have to be involved in the creation of cyclones, stable *regular* cyclones of increased strength may already exist with climate changes.

At this point, humans may be localized to Antarctica already, but the cyclones could be picking up genomes and further localizing them to the south pole. Once the tunnel is opened, the genomes are transferred down with the swirling oceanic water.

Interesting thing about cyclones is that those of higher strength can produce electric currents, and with those, a magnetic field which could provide protection from cosmic radiation (that could otherwise break DNA).

At the point this is happening, the Earth's global magnetic field will probably be gone. Note that the strength of cyclones and their poleward migration is expected to increase with climate change.

If Earth's magnetic field gets significantly weaker before the extensive network of lava tubes is created in Antarctica, humans will have to protect their houses from radiation. To achieve active protection, electric currents will have to flow through house walls, generating the protective magnetic field. Therefore, houses will probably be spherical or cylindrical, or in the form of circular pyramids (which is probably the best choice, considering environmental conditions among other things).

Interestingly, this is exactly the shape of pyramidal neuron cells. Also interesting is the fact that this house will either attract or repel charged cyclones (depending on the orientation of the magnetic field, which depends on the direction of electric current). Is it possible that such houses, engulfed in cyclones, will represent migrating [precursor] neural cells and, within them, living individuals to deep Earth? Magnetic fields do provide opportunities for physical guidance.

Assuming structural integrity is conserved, there are some benefits of having a house engulfed in a cyclone. The house could not only save electricity (no need to produce its own strong magnetic field) but if cyclone strength is oscillating or fluctuating, electricity to power the house could be generated. If the house exterior is allowed to rotate with the cyclone, oscillation is not even required, as the house could generate power similarly to a wind turbine. It may also be

possible to *harvest* the energy from electric discharges within the cyclone and store them in batteries. And cyclones can be very stable (as those on Jupiter clearly demonstrate). It is also interesting that electric discharges can stimulate the growth of some fungi and produce a fertilizer from atmospheric nitrogen. As, obviously, the food will have to be grown inside the house (cell). Water may also be collected from the cyclone.

The potential seems to exist for a long-term self-sustaining closed system.

Globalization is currently on the decline. We are witnessing major economies imploding and countries concentrating more and more on themselves rather than on others. If Trump gets re-elected in 2024 (and he probably will) this will also probably be the end of NATO. And survival of EU already seems less likely with every day. With environmental changes, depleting resources and associated wars it is obvious that world population is fragmenting and self-sustainability is becoming more and more important.

I interpret the happenings of today as precursors of the above hypothesized closed systems.

However, the problem with cyclones, regarding the energy harvesting potential, is that the central area (eye of the cyclone) is calm. Energy is concentrated mostly in the eyewall of the cyclone, and in typical tropical cyclones the eye has a diameter of at least 30 km. Such large houses are probably not plausible. And if billions of people will be migrating, the cyclones have to be smaller. How plausible are stable and sufficiently strong, small scale cyclones?

Probably not without involving large scale gravitons, which, however I wouldn't rule out. These could come from the fragmentation of a larger graviton, correlated with the fragmentation of Earth's magnetic field.

What would be the scale of forming cells, or houses?

I have done some calculations before[45] and the obtained cell radius is 69.5 m, or 139 m - with two individuals per cell. This is, however, the average size. Two groups will probably exist (small and large pyramidal cells).

Average radius of one group may be:

$$\sqrt{\left(\frac{230.34\text{ m}}{2}\right)^2 \times 2} = 162.87\text{ m}$$

where 230.34 m is the length of the sides of the base of the Great Pyramid in Giza (will be elaborated later - in short, dimensions of the Great Pyramid are exactly equal to the dimensions of a pyramidal neuron cell scaled from human scale to Earth's scale).

Average radius of the other group is then:

$$(139 \times 2) - 162.87 = 115.13\text{ m}$$

Average radii of uncompressed Jupiter cyclones (cells) are 2170 km (north pole) and 3140 km (south pole). The cells on Earth will be smaller but the ratio between the two groups should probably be the same, and, using the values obtained, indeed it is:

$$\frac{115.13}{162.87} \approx \frac{2170}{3140} \approx 0.7$$

Figure 4: Precursor pyramidal neuron cell

The question is whether such cell would contain naked souls or souls coupled with living bodies. In the case of the latter, perhaps the body would be limited to a brain.

I'm not sure how realistic is the above scenario. Without involving some 3rd party, it might not be. I have previously predicted that the activity of UFO/UAP phenomena should increase during the strong evolution event such as this one. This is based on the assumption that their habitats are located somewhere deep, either at the bottom of the oceans or deeper. With increasing magmatic and tectonic activity they could be forced to migrate upward. However, as multiple interpretations are common in nature, the reason for their upward migration might also be the downward migration of humans - in which they might have some more direct role.

How similar is the deep migration to standard migration process of neural cells, as shown in Fig. 5?

Is guidance to designated layers completely magnetic or does it involve some form of radial glial fibers (which at this scale, could be interpreted as plant-like fibers)?

Does the cell, at arrival, grow axons and dendrite equivalents? Probably, we already know that fungi do this.

Figure 5: Neuron generation and migration in the mouse neocortex⁴⁶

Plants here should probably be taken very relative, depending on pressures and temperatures, plants in deep Earth may be far from resembling plants on the surface. However, as noted before, areas in the mantle are hypothesized to exist where pressures and temperatures would not differ much from those on the surface or in the oceans. This should be enabled with presence of multiple gravitational maxima (real or induced) at different radii inside Earth (so the gravity is, at some point, cancelled between them).

In any case, migration from lava tubes towards the deep is probably synchronized with the end of a 2nd order cycle (which has an average period of about 26 million years). This is hypothesized to occur with the collapse of the Sun's core graviton and it should create a much larger disturbance of the system than the end of a 3rd order cycle. It has been calculated that this collapse lasts about 7 days, equally to the calculated migration time, so the two events probably are indeed synchronized. At this point the lava tubes are inundated

with the oceanic water (large scale cerebrospinal fluid equivalent) carrying the cells towards the interior. This process will probably be synchronized with the expulsion of greenhouse gases at the antipodal location, eventually resulting in a CO₂ dominating atmosphere on surface (dominating gas may initially be methane - but it will be relatively quickly oxidized to CO₂). Again, due to relative causality, precursor methane is already seeping in the Arctic.

5 Heaven and hell

	L2py	L3py	L4sp	L4ss	L4py	L5st	L5tt	L6cc	L6ct	L6inv
SOMATA										
L1	34									
L2	1,074	52								
L3	725	1,501	413	113						
L4		1,028	1,024	2,336	517					
L5		67	248	4		1,446	1,106	719	260	12
L6								648	3,711	778
DENDRITE [m]										
L1	7.9	2.7				0.9	3.4			
L2	15.4	5.7	0.1		0.5	0.8	2.1			
L3	8.9	20.3	2.2	0.3	1.3	0.7	0.9			
L4	0.1	21.3	5.0	8.1	6.2	2.0	1.5	0.4	2.3	
L5		1.7	0.9	0.3		16.6	21.9	10.4	13.0	2.6
L6						0.1	0.2	8.7	37.2	11.1
AXON [m]										
L1	16.1	15.3	2.1	0.3	0.3	14.0	1.1	1.2	0.1	0.7
L2	46.5	45.7	19.4	12.3	8.8	45.0	3.0	5.7	0.7	1.5
L3	38.6	84.0	48.6	43.6	22.6	47.5	3.7	24.7	2.2	2.9
L4	12.2	73.4	43.5	59.5	19.9	22.5	5.5	35.0	9.6	3.8
L5	38.3	117.5	17.2	24.7	26.1	42.9	31.2	90.5	38.0	45.7
L6	6.8	20.3	4.9	3.6	3.3	9.6	12.1	96.0	59.3	67.7

Figure 6: Number of somata and length of dendrites and axon that each of the 10 major excitatory cell types contributes to each of the six layers in a column of a rat barrel cortex⁴⁷

Most homo. β occupied cells are probably destined to become pyramidal brain cells of type ULpy (upper-layer pyramidal neuron), subtype L2py. Distribution of these cells should be similar to the distribution in Fig. 6.

Fused β .neutralum proteins (human neutralum individuals) may occupy layer I of the Earth (brain) mantle, unless these remain on surface.

Fused β .polarized individuals and human/animal products will then occupy layer II, while layer III is mostly reserved for animal/animal fusion products.

Interestingly, in the Hebrew Book of Enoch (which the church did not consider important enough to include in the Bible), the Enoch was taken on a journey with angels (which probably are highly correlated with UFO/UAP phenomena) who showed him a mountain with 4 recesses, 3 dark (housing evil souls) and one light (housing just souls), where souls

were awaiting judgement. The 3 dark recesses could be interpreted as entrances to the 3 layers here (the light one may represent a connection to the surface, or a near-surface layer). The book says the good will eat from the Tree of Life and regain the earthly body. The Tree of Life here probably should be correlated with DNA. It is possible that the *angels* represent some beings that have a crucial role in planetary neurogenesis events. By my theories, human souls highly correlate with DNA. It is possible then that the angels will regrow the bodies of some people using their DNA and the souls that were previously coupled to the original bodies will now couple to these cloned bodies. This then can be interpreted as resurrection.

The exact location (depth) should be proportional to the amount of polarization, inversely proportional to the intelligence potential[48].

The destination layer (depth) N may then be obtained by something like this:

$$N = 1 + 2|I_M - I_S|$$

$$I_M + I_S = 1$$

$$I_M = \frac{1}{4}a, \quad I_S = \frac{1}{4}b$$

$$a, b \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$$

where I_S and I_M are normalized spiritual and material intelligence[48] of the individual, respectively.

5.1 Total number of neocortex neurons, or hell inhabitants

What is the total number of neocortex neurons in Earth (homo. Ω species)?

In the analysis of the Solar System, I have found that the Earth is most likely a large scale equivalent of a localized composite (relative superposition) of 2 positrons and 1 anti-down quark (or, alternatively, 2 electrons and 1 down quark, but this is irrelevant in this context). This translates to two souls of equal mass and one soul that is about 9.4 times more massive. Coupling all these to the neocortex, the neocortex should be a superposition of the 3 neocortices of 2 species (male and female of one species plus one of other species). Humans, being the dominant mammals on Earth (but likely not the most intelligent - with introverted intelligence taken into account), probably represent one of these species in the current event. The most intelligent animals on the surface

of Earth are probably cetaceans, so the other species may be cetacean. Taking into account mass relationship, with polarized human male and female souls representing two relative positron equivalents, the other species could be long-finned pilot whales. With about 10 billion neurons in human neocortex[49] and about 12 billion in the neocortex of a long-finned pilot whale (studies report 37 billion[50], but this value is obtained via the optical fractionator method, known to produce overestimates, the actual value should be 2-3 times lower), one obtains about 32 billion total ($2 \times 10 + 12$). However, there are 6 major neurogenesis events (correlated with 6 major mass extinctions). Does this imply that 32 billion neurons are evolved with every event, resulting in $6 \times 32 = 192$ billion neurons total? No. What evolves in every event is a superposition of neurons of the 3 neocortices and this superposition is equal to $(10 + 10 + 12) / 3 = 10.666'$ billion neuron cells. Multiplying this 6 times, one obtains 64 billion neuron cells total.

This does not imply that humans (and long-finned pilot whales) are cultivated on Earth's surface prior to each major mass extinction. Although that is a possibility, it's probably not the case. Different neurons occupy different neocortex layers and different layers may be populated in different neurogenesis events (albeit with some overlap). This only implies that the number of neurons generated in each event is, on average, the same.

But should one calculate with the current estimates (which probably represent the peak in case of humans)? Horizontal gene transfer will lead to hybridization. Assuming polarized humans hybridize with canine species (which I consider as the most likely hybridization, on average), the number of neocortex neurons in humans could decrease to the superposition average of humans and dogs, giving $(10.2 + 10.2 + 0.5) / 3 = 7$ billion neurons (assuming superposition of human male, human female and a *Canis familiaris* - with an average number of neocortex neurons of 500 million[51]). Assuming now that the number of neocortex neurons in a long-finned pilot whale is about 18 billion (about 1/2 instead of 1/3 of the overestimate) or that it is going to increase to that number (e.g., in a superposition with orca - who probably have the most neocortex neurons of all mammals), the total number becomes $6 \times (7 + 7 + 18) / 3 = 64$ billion, again.

Alternative calculation involves biomass of the species, rather than the average mass of individuals of the species. Total biomass of humans is about 390 Mt (million tonnes), while the mass of wild marine mammals is about 40 Mt[52], so the ratio of masses is here inverted. Assuming, however, that the median number of neurons in wild marine mammals is 11 billion, with 10 billion in humans, the total number of neurons here is $6 \times (10 + 11 + 11) / 3$, again 64 billion.

Interestingly, some estimate the total number of wild mammals on Earth at about 130 billion[53]. With two mammals per cell, this gives 65 billion cells,

suggesting 6×65 billion for the total number of neurons (or more, with humans included). However, most wild animals probably represent extracellular biomass, except possibly large whales, who might represent progenitor cells themselves. Most likely intracellular biomass are the domesticated species (including humans).

5.2 Distribution

For the total number of neocortex neurons in homo.Ω, $n = 64 \times 10^9$, extrapolating from Fig. 6:

total number of forming brain cells in the current neurogenesis event, assuming population of top 3 layers dominates:

$$n_f = \frac{34 + 1074 + 725}{17816} 64 \times 10^9 = \frac{1833}{17816} 64 \times 10^9 = 6\,584\,643\,018$$

number of *fused* individuals in layer I:

$$n_1 = 2 \times \frac{34}{1833} \times 6584643018 = 244\,274\,809$$

number of *fused* individuals in layer II:

$$n_2 = 2 \times \frac{1074}{1833} \times 6584643018 = 7\,716\,210\,149$$

number of *fused* individuals in layer III:

$$n_3 = 2 \times \frac{725}{1833} \times 6584643018 = 5\,208\,801\,078$$

Total individuals required:

$$n_1 + n_2 + n_3 = 2n_f = 13\,169\,286\,036$$

At the time of this writing, number of human individuals is:

$$n_{dh} = 7.752 \times 10^9,$$

number of domesticated mammals (even-toed ungulates[54], odd-toed ungulates[55], carnivorans[56]):

$$n_{df} = 4.22 \times 10^9 + 108 \times 10^6 + 1.5 \times 10^9 = 5\,828\,000\,000,$$

giving the total number of:

$$n_{dh} + n_{df} = 13\,580\,000\,000$$

The obtained number closely matches the requirement (the majority of the surplus individuals may be transformed to non-mammalian species, some - unpaired (neutral), may remain on surface, and few may end up in even deeper layers).

Note that the number of individuals in layer 3 closely matches the number of domesticated mammals, so this layer may be reserved for them - the surplus may go to layer II (however, it is possible that at least some domesticated mammals should be associated with glial cells, not neurons).

What are *fused* individuals?

I hypothesize that, during strong evolution, symbiosis between animals is, at least in some cases, precursor to the *fossilization* of that symbiosis into a new distinct organism, a chimera of symbionts. In case of humans, I hypothesize *fusion* or convergence of polarized human subspecies with subspecies of domesticated animals, forming new species, which I refer to as homo.gamma. This convergence is slow during weak evolution, however, in strong evolution events it is accelerated, being dominated by horizontal gene transfer.

The prophecies, or religions based on them, showing fused forms (chimeras) living together with non-fused individuals, confirm not only this hybridization during strong evolution, but also the existence of subspecies which do not *fuse* with other animals (they might be *fusing* with other people, however, conserving human form).

Note that more than 2 species may be involved in the creation of chimeras.

5.2.1 Homo model

The above calculation is based on a rat brain model, which seems appropriate in case of Earth, at least at this point of evolution.

The most populous mammals on Earth are humans, but they are closely followed by rats. Human population growth has, however, reached its maximum it seems, while the population growth of rats has accelerated in recent times - as expected with climate change. It seems likely that rats will outnumber humans at the end of the current Earth's neurogenesis event. However, the human neocortex has, on average, 10.2 billion neurons, and that number is very close to the estimated plateau of human population size. Of course, in Earth, humanoid neurons would form only a part of the neocortex neural network.

If one correlates neutralums with Rh- individuals, Earth is currently in superposition of scaled rat brain and human brain. Which model will prevail in the end depends solely on polarization at time of differentiation. The evolution is accelerating and blood types will be evolving at accelerating pace, whether they will evolve into depolarized types or not depends on individuals - whether they remain cancerous or not. Although, number of neurons for homo model should be equal, there are differences in number of neurons per layer.

Number of neurons in layers II and III does not change significantly, but the number in layer I increases, at the expense of neuron number in deeper layers (IV - VI).

Assuming 5 times increase:

$$n_f = \frac{5 \times 34 + 1074 + 725}{17816} 64 \times 10^9 = \frac{1969}{17816} 64 \times 10^9 = 7\,073\,192\,636$$

$$n_1 = 2 \times \frac{5 \times 34}{1969} \times n_f = 1\,221\,374\,046$$

$$n_2 = 2 \times \frac{1074}{1969} \times n_f = 7\,716\,210\,148$$

$$n_3 = 2 \times \frac{725}{1969} \times n_f = 5\,208\,801\,078$$

giving the total:

$$n_1 + n_2 + n_3 = 2n_f = 14\,146\,385\,272$$

This is 566 385 272 more than the estimated current population of 13 580 000 000. Assuming that population of domestic animals doesn't increase significantly so the contribution mainly comes from human population increase, the required number, according to current projections[57], will be reached in year 2026.

Note that it is likely that human population will grow beyond the requirement, but, being unsustainable, it will be reduced. Significant reduction probably can be expected with predicted natural disturbances (climate change, earthquakes/volcanism, asteroid impacts).

5.3 The number of the beast

If the Moon collapses into 3 maxima (as may have happened on Mars), which could be required if it corresponds to 3 layers to be populated, then there should be 3 distinct pulses of *extinctions* (transformations), possibly separated by decades.

I have shown previously that the thicknesses of Earth's mantle layers are proportional to the periods between major mass extinctions[58]. Collapse into 3 maxima is further justified due to the fact that precisely 3 discontinuities in the mantle require small adjustment for layers to match these periods perfectly. Even the calculated 3 adjustments, each being 1/2 of the larger, correlate well with the sizes of 3 rifts on Mars (Valles Marineris).

Calculated years of impacts (in the analysis of the Solar System) could thus be mapped to particular *days*, as shown in Table 2.

<i>Day</i>	Year	CO ₂	Notes	Year alternative (low time compression)
0	2016	400	anti-christ birth (conception correlated with the Chelyabinsk meteorite in 2013)	2016
1	2029±2	450	soul-body transformation peak (anti-christ maturity), possible asteroid impact(s)	2094±12
2	2040±1	500	polarized soul-body transformation peak, partial migration towards Antarctica (with a precursor migration towards the north), possible smaller meteorites	2160±6
3	2048±2	550	age of confusion, divorce/divergence of neutral and polarized species, magnetic field excursion, possible impacts	2208±12
4	2055±3	600	polarized soul-body transformation peak, collapse of most mainstream religion - resurrection of truth, establishment of the neutrality era, migration to Antarctica, possible smaller meteorites	2250±18
5	2061±2	650	soul-body transformation peak, possible impacts (possible correlation with the Halley's comet)	2286±12
6	2066±2	700	transmigration year, anti-christ death, god rests in peace	2316±12
7	2071±2	750	deconception of complex surface life complete	2346±12

Table 2: 7 *days* of the 6th (neuro)genesis event

Of course, considering that it was previously determined that Earth's day is 83-84 human years, using the same term ("day") for a different interval here might be confusing. If one Earth's day is 84 human years, the interval here of 42 years from 2029 - 2071 should be equal to 1/2 Earth days or 12 Earth hours. However, during accelerated evolution the time intervals are effectively compressing, and since the intervals are compressing here and there are 7 intervals (like 7 days in a week) I find it convenient to use "days" here as well (relativity would not be complete without relativity in the amount of relativity itself).

Note that *days* here are mapped to particular atmospheric CO₂ concentration, this is based on the assumption that atmospheric CO₂ currently follows the rate of evolution on Earth. One *day* is equal to the interval of time during which the amount of CO₂ in the atmosphere increases by 50 ppm (this kind of quantization has been theorized in the Solar System analysis[27]). Since the CO₂ is rising exponentially the *days* are then shortening with time. Also, at this point it is still hard to believe that all these events will occur during the 21st century, rather than be spread out over a longer period (e.g., up to the 24th century). A much better prognosis should, however, become possible by the year 2032.

In standard embryonic neurogenesis, migration of cells starts once the peak of progenitor neuron population is reached, but cells do not migrate all at once. Conventional estimates for the peak of human population range from 2040 - 2084. I estimate that the global peak will be centred about the year 2063±3. Regionally, population peaks could happen some

time before or after that year. Migration towards Antarctica could then indeed occur in waves, but migration towards the interior might occur only once all the polarized individuals are concentrated at the pole - in the lava tubes.

In standard neurogenesis, the peak typically occurs mid-gestation, at about 120 days on average (the range is 105 - 140 days[59]). Assuming that Earth's day, as calculated before (here, and differently, in the Solar System analysis), lasts 83-84 human years, the 120 days of the current Earth's neurogenesis cycle gestation period would be equal to about 10000 human years. The 140 days (maximum for the peak) is equal to about 11700 human years (11620 in case of a 83-year day, 11760 for one day equal to 84 years). Very interestingly, 11700 years ago (more precisely, 11700 ± 99 years before the year 2000 AD[60]) was the start of the Holocene. Thus, it appears that the start of Holocene was also the start of the gestation period and the peak has to occur by year 2060 ± 99 at most. Considering the fact that the peak has been reached in some large regions already (e.g., China in 2022[61]), and that projections are being revised down over time (and considering that the peak human population should probably at most be equal to the average number of neocortex neurons in humans - 10.2 billion), my estimate for the global peak in year 2063 ± 3 seems very reasonable. Note that this estimate is in agreement with the previously calculated year of the [end of the] Judgement Day (2066 ± 2). However, human infertility could peak sooner, 2040-2048, with the population growth continuing through genetic cloning and hybridization.

Note that the population peak in this century is probably necessary [or the last chance] for healthy Earth's neurogenesis, otherwise the interpretation of humans transforms from neural progenitors to a malignant tumour and both Earth and all life on Earth would be gone within about 300 years in that case[62]. Thus, signs of near human population peak are good signs and good news for sustainability of life of Earth and in Earth.

It should be noted, that in conventional neurogenesis, precursor neuron cells are generated in the fluid-filled ventricular zone, which represents the inner wall of a neural tube. Neural tube is formed from the neural plate, which represents an evolved ectoderm (surface layer). Precursor neuron cells arise from the neural progenitor cells, which are cultivated on the ectoderm (crust). Thus, it is these cells that humans living on Earth's surface should probably be associated with. In Earth, as noted before, it is the lava tubes that most likely represent neural tubes that will be occupied by humans. Thus, migrating humans will probably settle here (close to the surface, below the south pole) for awhile before they continue migration. Migration to these tubes will be stimulated by diverse ways - it is clear already that the surface habitability

is declining. These tubes will, however, become filled with salty water (equivalent of the cerebro-spinal fluid filling the ventricular zones in standard neurogenesis), however, the neuron cells themselves should be filled with freshwater (equivalent of cytoplasm). This suggests that humans living in these tubes will eventually evolve or hybridize into aquatic lifeforms or amphibian lifeforms (assuming pockets of air will exist within cells/tubes). Interestingly, there are interpretations of human history suggesting that ancient human civilizations have been in contact with aquatic or amphibian intra- or extra- terrestrials[63]. However, I find it more likely that only the knowledge of planetary neurogenesis has been in some way communicated to them, possibly by beings associated with UFO/UAP phenomena, who themselves, however, may be amphibian and living below Earth's surface.

Interestingly, in years 2029 (*day 1*) and 2040 (*day 2*), Easter falls on April 1st[64], which could be interpreted as another signal, as these two years are predicted to be correlated with major events.

Assuming the predictions become true, the year 2040 could be the last year Easter will still be celebrated, among other things, because there may be no Moon as one knows it now (calculation of the date of Easter depends on the Moon).

And this is in agreement with the announced collapse of the great apostasy, Trinitarianism - Roman Catholicism, or the true AntiChrist, that was announced in Revelation. Newton arrived at the year 2060, but different calculations can yield a similar result.

I would put the birth of Trinitarianism at the superposition of years 382 (when the Biblical canon was officially recognized by the Council of Rome) and 397 (when the Council of Carthage finalized the canon as it is known today). The superposition gives a peak year:

$$\frac{382 + 397}{2} = 390$$

The period for which the Trinitarianism would reign should be, per Revelation, 1260 years. Naively, this would give year 1650 for the death of AntiChrist but no one interprets it as such, for a good reason.

Note that the year 1650 should be interpreted as the peak in superposition of years 1642 (382+1260) and 1657 (397+1260). Now note that the year 1642 is the year Newton (or shall one say Elijah) was born (by the Julian calendar in use in England at the time, year 1643 by the Gregorian calendar), I do not consider this a meaningless coincidence.

If it took 390 years for the AntiChrist to be born after the birth of Christ it would be naive to expect the AntiChrist will die in a day. In other words, just as birth is preceded by conception and formation, death ends with deformation and deconception. Assuming symmetry between birth and death, deconception of the AntiChrist (church) should peak in/about the year:

$$390 + 1260 + 390 = 2040$$

Other two significant years could be 2024 (382+1260+382) and 2054 (397+1260+397).

If, however, one rounds the 397 (390) to 400, one gets the same result as Newton:

$$400 + 1260 + 400 = 2060$$

But of course, this should be understood as a rough estimate, as some asymmetry should exist between the two periods (the one preceding birth and the one trailing death). Also, Jesus was born a couple of years before 1 AD (there is no year 0 AD), 6 years at most, so one might want to take that into account. I have earlier came to conclusion that he was most likely born in the year 5 BC, on June 3rd[25]. Thus, 4 years, 6 months and 28 days should be added to 400 here. Now, asymmetry is likely to be exponential. Assuming it takes this form:

$$\frac{a}{10} = \frac{b}{a}$$

a = period preceding birth
b = period trailing death

one obtains the following year:

$$400 + a + 1260 + 400 + b = 400 + a + 1260 + 400 + \frac{a^2}{10} = 400 + 1666.66 = 2066.66$$

$$a = 4 + (6 \times 30 + 28) / 365.25 = 4.569 \text{ years}$$

A very interesting result, as this date is also my birthday (2066.09.01) and calculated most likely age at death.

Note that the year 1666 that appears above was the Newton's "Miraculous Year"[65], the year that marked the peak of his achievements. Why this synchronicity with Newton? Well because he was another messenger of god, of course.

Note also that the hypothesized a/b relation does produce realistic results. E.g., for a period *a* (period preceding birth) of 6.76 months (equal to Newton's - he was born prematurely), it gives a period *b* (period trailing death) of 4.569 months, which does seem like a reasonable period of time for the soft tissue of a dead body to fully decompose[66]. For a period *a* of 10 months (equal to mine, also should be normal), the process is symmetric, giving a period *b* of 10 months as well. Again,

a reasonable estimate for a bare human body decomposing in normal fertile soil - which should be the natural decomposing environment that is symmetric to natural *in utero* development. So even here, one sees how humans are unbalanced, anti-god and unsustainable - by burying bodies protected in caskets deep in the soil, the decomposition may last 10 times longer or more, depraving the god's land of nutrients that were taken 10 times faster from the land to feed the body in the uterus.

In any case, I would not be surprised if the last day of *day 6* occurs in the year 66 of the millennium, on the part 666 of the thousand parts of the year, the day of my birthday, Elijah's new death and my new birth.. day. But I would also not be surprised if it doesn't occur exactly at the calculated date, uncertainties always exist.

From all this one can conclude that the church will finally be dead by the year 2040, after which year only its rotting stench will plague the lands, before it expires completely by the year 2066. Are we talking here about the Catholic church (cult) exclusively? I do not. The death may be correlated with the ongoing extinction, rot may be correlated with hydrogen sulphide, which can be correlated with climate change, which has been kickstarted by the church of holy humanity. For it is clear as *day* that the the whole human civilization is a cult, only the *gods* and the *churches* differ between different institutions.

5.4 Deep Six

Similar hierarchy is present in layers IV - VI. These layers have been populated during previous major mass *extinctions* and so they contain fused (strongly evolved) forms of surface animals present at the time, such as dinosaurs. Here, potentially humanoid ones are mostly contained within deep-layer pyramidal cells (DLpy).

6 Salvation in pyramids

I have previously correlated major mass extinctions with Earth's mantle layers and associated neurogenesis events. However, minor extinctions exist as well, and so should minor strong evolution events, even if these may not include migration of life into Earth's interior. In any case, salient representative of standard neuron cells is a pyramidal neuron cell. If such cells (or similar precursors) are created on the surface during strong evolution events, some of these cells may fail to migrate for some reason, stay trapped on surface and fossilize. There are a lot of pyramidal structures/formations on Earth, and they've been found on Mars as well. Could some of these be remnants of pyramidal neuron cells? If so, primary candidates should probably be natural formations, such as pyramidal hills or mountains, like the one found in Antarctica[67] (although a

triangular shape may be more convincing).

Considering that the entry point for cells during migration events should be located somewhere about the South pole, such fossils in Antarctica may not be surprising. Furthermore, there's a fairly good chance that this entrance is highly correlated with Mount Erebus[68], which is, interestingly, in the same area where the peak named The Pyramid Peak and the trough named The Pyramid Trough are located. Now that's some interesting synchronicity. The peak may not be a fossil, but it could be interpreted as a symbol of the entrance. More convincing as a fossil, however, would be the Mount Discovery (which is, interestingly, located just to the west of The Pyramid Peak) - it is triangular and even contains a three-armed mass resembling basal dendrites of neurons (the three arms are even all roughly the same size). However, it seems too large to represent a fossilized cell, and it is questionable whether the migrating cell should have grown dendrites. However, growth of dendrites may not be surprising for a cell stuck at surface, and even the giant size could be explained by the surface environment (lack of competition, lower pressure).

Considering requirements for fossilization, how can a fossil like this be created? By the conventional paradigm, in order to fossilize, the living cell must have been, after/during death, buried quickly under sediment. Assuming the sediment hardened and was massive enough, the intrusion of magma from below could fossilize the shape. The original sediment may have eroded afterwards, however, depending what it was made of, some layering could be preserved. This fossilization mechanism is unusual, but may be plausible in this particular place during the cataclysmic neurogenesis events.

It is unknown of what kind of material the cell walls of this scale would be made of, but, depending on the conditions in the hypothesized habitable zones in Earth's mantle, it is possible that the structure-supporting material itself has to be very strong. In that case, it probably would be, to a significant degree, inorganic (similarly to bones in the bodies of standard animals). If the structure is strong/massive enough perhaps it could withstand the lava/ash bombardment from a nearby volcano, at least long enough for the lava to harden and the shape to be preserved. In that case, magma intrusion from below may be unnecessary. However, current scientific understanding is that the Mt Discovery represents a volcanic cone. Magma intrusion is also likely when the nature/mechanics of nutrient acquisition of the cell is considered. Standard neuron cells acquire nutrients from the surrounding blood vessels. Since on this scale, blood equivalent is the magma itself, intrusion would not be surprising. In fact, this may be how the cell got killed - it is reasonable to assume that the pressure of magma is regulated in mantle layers, however, here

the pressure of magma may have been too high, resulting in the destruction of the cell.
 In any case, deeper analysis of the rock could potentially provide more support for, or against, the fossilization hypothesis.

What about the artificially looking pyramids? These are unlikely to be fossils, but some could be correlated with planetary neurogenesis and beings that may be associated with UFO/UAP phenomena.

Scaling the largest pyramid, the Great Pyramid of Giza, to the scale of humans, one obtains the size of:

$$h_n = \frac{h}{R} \times R_h = \frac{146.694}{6371000} \times 1 = 23 \times 10^{-6} m = 23 \mu m$$

h_n = pyramidal cell body (soma) length
 h = Giza pyramid height (m)
 R = Earth radius (m)
 R_h = human radius (m)

Considering that the average mammalian pyramidal cell soma (body) is 20 μm in length, this is a remarkable agreement.

Here, 1 m was used as an approximation for a human radius, but one may try to define it precisely.

To define human radius one must know its centre. In one interpretation, this is the navel. Thus, the radius of a human (as a particle) may be defined as the arithmetic mean of polar and equatorial radii - distances from navel to the top of the head, bottom of the feet and average equatorial radius of the body. Using my own dimensions:

$$R_h = \frac{0.75 + 1.04 + 0.18}{3} = 0.66 m$$

Here, I assumed average equatorial radius is equal to the distance from the navel to the left or right of the body.

Taking also the base of the pyramid into account (assuming inversely proportional relationship between height and base side length), this gives:

$$h_n = \frac{h + l}{2} \times \frac{R_h}{R} = \frac{146.694 + 230.34}{2} \times \frac{0.66}{6371000} = 19.53 \times 10^{-6} m = 19.53 \mu m$$

Using data for the second largest pyramid, one of Khafre (Chephren), yields similar results. Other pyramids are mostly about 50 m in height and probably

have a different origin (Egyptian). Apparently one could separate them into different groups by size - the same as pyramidal cells are grouped in human brain (size depends on the layer).

The similarity in shape and size between pyramids and neuron cells is unlikely to be a meaningless coincidence, it can certainly be interpreted as an unconscious signal, but may be more than that.

One may thus consider the following scenarios:

1. the constructors knew the size of the pyramidal neuron cell (and Earth radius) and consciously constructed great pyramids in these proportions, possibly as a signal for us,
2. the great pyramids are the Earth's real fossilized pyramidal neuron cells or precursor neuron cells (more likely, as these can be artificial-looking, similar to how our houses may be interpreted as precursor cells),
3. the great pyramids in the original form were houses (shelters) of some members of an *alien* civilization, constructed using advanced machinery (e.g., 3D printing), the synchronicity involved was not conscious on their part (note that these shelters can still be interpreted as precursor neuron cells).

There is plenty of evidence suggesting early Egyptians were more materialistic than spiritual (they seem to have been even more obsessed with preservation of bodies than the modern civilization) and they certainly did not have the ability to measure the size of a neuron soma.

The theory of planetary neurogenesis implies that such neurogenesis has taken place on Venus and Mars too. Due to relative equivalence in neural cells and proteins, evolution of surface life must have been relatively equal to Earth's (although accelerated and quantitatively different). Mars' and Venus' humans have likely visited Earth, just like humans from Earth will be visiting Mars. 3D printing using resources *in situ* is the possible method humans are going to use on Mars to construct shelters.

According to some researchers and analyses, at least some of the stone blocks of Giza pyramids were cast *in situ* rather than carved at a remote place. In such case, the quality of the concrete used would strengthen the 3rd hypothesis - its sophistication and endurance would be an enigma to modern science[69], suggesting the constructors were (unknowingly, if Egyptians) the pioneers of nanotechnology.

This hypothesis, however, was later refuted[70] by others[71] (although one should differentiate between repairs, done by Egyptians, and the original work, likely done by someone else - something not taken into account in these studies). Convincing arguments for the casting of some blocks still do exist[72].

In any case, two greatest pyramids are in several aspects different from other pyramids, casting strong doubt on Egyptians being the original builders.

The analysis of building material shows that the limestone formed from a sea bottom sediment[71].

This may go in favour of the 2nd hypothesis - the cells are supposed to be transferred by CSF (pH 7.33 ocean) to deep mantle layers. It is possible some got stuck, or ceased to develop completely, and dried (although, I have predicted that cells, if created, are created on the south pole).

However, that limestone was not deposited where Giza pyramids are now.

The fossil hypothesis here is very unrealistic - considering the construction precision and artificial look of the interior (unless we assume this was a subsequent artificial modification), the mixture of granite and limestone blocks.

However, an *alien* structure of such size would explain religion in old Egyptian Kingdom - encounter with such structure would likely spur beliefs in supernatural phenomena (gods) and even worshipping of structures themselves.

The fact that there are no inscriptions inside two greatest pyramids supports this hypothesis - they probably considered them sacred and instead of using the pyramids themselves, they went and tried to make copies. Whatever they've found inside made them believe in life after death in underworld and that the pyramids were portals to afterlife.

Note that this aligns perfectly with the theory of neurogenesis - pyramidal neuron cells (pyramids) are transported to deep mantle layers (underworld) in the process, so maybe they've even found some details on this inside.

Note 1:

Some inscriptions were found in Khufu pyramid, however, these certainly look like a hoax and can hardly be even called inscriptions, especially when compared to inscriptions in other pyramids.

No mummies were found either in two greatest pyramids. I do not consider that important (mummies were missing from most pyramids), but some claim that Khufu and Khafre were buried outside of the pyramids out of fear their bodies would be defiled by people (they were cruel rulers).

That does not seem to make sense - to build the greatest tomb to secure afterlife and then decide to be buried somewhere else as an anonymous? How angry would then these people be, knowing they've built these pyramids for nothing?

Given the reputation of Khufu and Khafre, I would not be surprised they did not treat these pyramids as sacred and untouchable as others did. They even might have claimed that the pyramids were built for them.

Note 2:

That Egyptians were trying to imitate the great pyramids becomes obvious when one compares the building angle of the pyramids, chronologically[73].

- 2600 BC - building the pyramid at Meidum with inclination ($51^{\circ}50'35''$) almost identical to the inclination of the Great (Khufu) Pyramid ($51^{\circ}50'40''$),
- 2600 BC - believing the Meidum was stable they've started building Bent pyramid in Dahshur with an even steeper angle (54°) to imitate the Khafre pyramid (53°), but in the meantime the Meidum pyramid collapsed and they've decided to decrease the angle to $43^{\circ}22'$,
- 2580 BC - convinced now that this new angle is stable (Bent pyramid did not collapse) the Egyptians built Red pyramid at Dahshur from the start at exactly the same angle as the one Bent was completed at ($43^{\circ}22'$).

Now, Khufu and Khafre pyramids were supposedly built after the Red pyramid (allegedly completed 2560 BC and 2530 BC, respectively). Why would they now start building their greatest pyramids at an angle proven to be unstable on a smaller pyramid? Especially when the angle they've used on their largest pyramid (Red) so far, was proven stable? They did not dare to risk anything with the Red pyramid, and that one is still much smaller than Khufu and Khafre pyramids. It is clear why they would not want to risk this - the construction took long time and if the pyramid would collapse midway through construction there simply wouldn't be enough time to build another one before the pharaoh dies. If they did have the need for that special angle (why, if not trying to imitate something *sacred* that leads to afterlife?), would they not try building a stable smaller pyramid at that angle and then build the larger pyramid instead of risking so much?

The pyramid of Menkaure (the 3rd pyramid in Giza) which has almost the same angle ($51^{\circ}20'25''$) as the Khufu pyramid would be a good candidate for such a pyramid, but this one was built after the Khufu and Khafre pyramids, \approx 2500 BC (Menkaure, or Mykerinus, was a son of Khafre and grandson of Khufu).

The above alone, for me, is a very convincing evidence that the Egyptians did not build *Khufu* and *Khafre* pyramids. These two must be the oldest pyramids in Egypt and Menkaure is *only* the best imitation Egyptians ever managed to construct (although it's still possible they weren't original builders of this one either, they certainly did maintenance work on Giza monuments, but the origin should be questionable).

Here's what probably happened:

Khufu did not want to risk building another pyramid like the Red as he wasn't convinced this is an imitation good enough to secure afterlife. Thus, he arranged a secret chamber in the Great Pyramid,

wrote '*Friends of Khufu*' on the wall, and, afterwards, arranged for the chamber to be *accidentally* discovered, together with the message - which was supposed to convince people the gods built the pyramid for him. People might have suspected he was behind this, and that was one reason why they didn't love him much.

He probably also forced people to do maintenance work on the outer walls of the pyramid as he assumed the original was smooth and polished on the outside.

Then he might have told people that the other pyramid was, likewise, built for his descendant, although I wouldn't be surprised if there is a secret chamber in Khafre pyramid too, with a message '*Friends of Khafre*'. After their deaths, it may be that anger rather than pure robbery was behind the removal of their bodies from the *tombs* of the two pyramids.

Given the apocalyptic events during strong evolution, in order to stay anchored and safe on the surface, any construction must be made of heavy, and probably not easily magnetized, material.

The massive stones and overly mass filled interior is the obvious choice for such construction. With everything considered, it certainly seems like the builders (aware of planetary neurogenesis) tried to avoid being pulled into Earth's interior (which is why this was built in equatorial region and not on the south pole, even though the south pole should be more habitable during strong evolution). This was their way to secure their stay on the surface during the extreme events, rather than a portal to the *underworld*.

The massive entrance doors which can be easily opened from inside also support the hypothesis, as well as the fact that the Giza plateau (or, more precisely, Giza cuesta) is more than 60 meters above sea level.

Note that if all ice on Earth melts, sea level would rise by approximately 70 meters. However, all chambers in the pyramid would stay above the sea level, even the original entrance which is 17 meters above the pyramid base. Why else would the entrance be at that height? And why does the tunnel running from the entrance continue underground? Sure, multiple interpretations are possible but one could be the fear of flooding.

If Egyptians are not the builders of this pyramid, some additional insulation (e.g., flood protection) and sealing material between the stones was likely present too.

Even the sarcophagus might be the sturdy last resort solution to stay alive, rather than a final resting place as Egyptians interpreted it.

I believe this was the true purpose of two greatest pyramids - they were both shelters, but even if that is not the case, apart from these mentioned above, there are other reasons to believe Egyptians were not the constructors:

- pictures and hieroglyphic inscriptions are common for small pyramids, it would be very odd to treat great pyramids differently if they were built by

the same people, materialistic people are proud people so they like to put inscriptions on whatever they build - do we seriously believe they would be proud of the small pyramids but not of the big ones if they'd built them both? Ridiculous,

- no construction plans, construction ramps and tools which can be unambiguously associated with two greatest pyramids,
- considering their religious beliefs, materialistic nature, the alleged purpose of the pyramids and average human lifetime at the time - an endeavour to build something that will surely require several decades of work does not seem likely.

There is no doubt that Egyptians built pyramids, there is also evidence they hauled stones to Giza, but reasons to insist that they were constructors of the greatest pyramids must be purely political (as part of associated cult ideology), rather than having a realistic basis in pursuit of truth.

6.1 In the eyes of Sphinx

The two greatest pyramids were probably not the only buildings in Giza not originally constructed by Egyptians. One other obvious candidate is the Sphinx.

It is well known that Egyptians did repairs on sacred buildings in Giza over the years. They are doing maintenance work on the Sphinx even today.

The repairs are not subtle. Dating the concrete collar on Sphinx's head, someone could conclude the Sphinx is 100 years old or less. This is why dating any of the casing stones on these big monuments is pretty much useless if one is interested in original builders.

Analysis of erosion indicates that the original building may pre-date the reign of Khufu[74]. Apparently, there are also some natural caves below the Sphinx. These too may be the clue to original builders, however, it was suggested that builders may still be Egyptians from an earlier dynasty.

Claims that some Egyptian dynasty has to be the builder of Sphinx and largest pyramids are based on the assumption that the builders were indigenous to Earth's surface - a civilization which would leave behind abundant evidence of its presence on that surface. This assumption also implies the place must have been habitable at the time of construction.

Since there are no signs of other civilizations (one could argue that the great structures themselves are pretty big signs but, with the abuse of the Occam's razor, any other explanation, no matter how far-fetched, is considered more likely), but there are abundant signs of old Egyptian kingdom, the [sacred] consensus is that Egyptians were the original builders. However, both Venus and Mars have been habitable in the past and, according to my theories, humans very

similar to us evolved on these planets too. Some might argue that these planets lost habitability long time ago, however, evidence shows that Mars' inanimate surface is periodically and at least partially punctuated with habitability that lasts for millions of years. In my theories, these are events of adult neurogenesis and it is entirely possible that humans or humanoids evolve even during these events. But even if that is not the case, at some point during these events the tunnel should be open between the surface and deep mantle where humanoid creatures should exist. Relatively recent humanoid visitors from Mars and Venus thus cannot be excluded. One cannot rule out humanoid visitors from subsurface Earth as well, or even from the bottom of the oceans.

Note that, unlike the pyramids, Sphinx is carved out of bedrock. While *3D-printing* (deposition of material layer by layer) was likely done by nature itself, some kind of 3D-carving apparatus might have been used for the original construction.

As a side note - like everything else, we obviously did not invent 3D-printing either but I'm sure it has been patented as human invention. It's really a wonder how Earth has not been sued for copyright infringement so far (even though it's obvious who is the original creator).

Perhaps the greatest evidence that Egyptians were not the original builders lies in the disproportionality between the Sphinx's body and its head. The head is simply too small for the body. This is very unusual for Egyptians who were very careful with proportions elsewhere. Their canon of proportions was used even in the oldest dynasty. Lack of inscriptions (like in case of the greatest pyramids) could be interpreted as another evidence.

Among those who argue for young Sphinx is R. Schneiker who claims the head has not been constructed more than 5000 years ago[75]. However, there's bias in his theory (I see it more as an attempt to defend the possibility of young Sphinx rather than a pursuit of truth) and, although it cannot be ruled out, I find more convincing and unbiased the analysis by Manichev/Parkhomenko who concluded that the Sphinx is older than 800 000 years[76].

Schneiker, for example, argues that annual flooding of the Nile would completely erode the Sphinx's head had it been constructed more than 5000 years ago. However, the fact is that the Sphinx is at such elevation that it never gets submerged by flooding. Even the ancient higher flooding would only inundate the Sphinx excavation if it existed, not the head. With human maintenance excluded, however, the body of the Sphinx would be completely covered in sand so there would be no damage of flooding even on the body. The head probably did experience significant erosion over time but the head was likely initially much bigger

as well (proportional to the body), it was only recarved later by Egyptians. However, the Sphinx would experience significant flooding more than 800 000 years ago, when the sea levels there were much higher.

With all dots connected, I see two possibilities here.

6.1.1 Possibility 1: The Sphinx was entirely constructed by Egyptians less than 5000 years ago

The Sphinx does not contain any rooms inside which may be another clue as to what it represents. Considering that and [lack of] other features, if Egyptians are the original builders of the Sphinx then I find the following scenario most likely - it is simply a repurpose of a failed attempt to replicate the Great Pyramid. Looking at the body of the Sphinx, it obviously has layers that make its sides look like giant staircases - the same as the Great Pyramid.

Suppose they started building a pyramid but they failed to predict the possible instability of a layer of sandstone (below the MECO hyperthermal) that now forms the neck of the Sphinx. Eventually they saw it will be a problem (perhaps it started collapsing as it was built) so they turned the building into a statue. Material that formed the upper (collapsed?) part of the pyramid and part of the sides too was now extra material that was likely used elsewhere (e.g., to build the nearby temples).

Now that they knew they can't build pyramids out of bedrock they realized they will have to manufacture and use stone blocks. So the Sphinx is a repurpose of the first failed attempt of Egyptian pyramid building. If that is not the case, why there aren't any other big structures carved out of bedrock in Egypt?

It is of course possible that Sphinx is simply made out of the leftover formation after the rock has been used for construction of other objects, but who left the leftover formation?

Probably the original builders of the Great Pyramid, whoever they are.

6.1.2 Possibility 2: Egyptians are reconstructors

The other possibility is that the base of the Sphinx was carved out earlier by someone else, perhaps by the original constructors of the Great Pyramid. They too must have brought the stone from somewhere for the construction of that pyramid. It would be logical they used a nearby formation.

If one looks at open pit human mines today one can notice the step-like layering. The original Sphinx base may have been created similarly. Perhaps the layering continued up to the top where the top of the Sphinx' head is now but the top collapsed due to erosion of limestone (e.g., with elevated levels of CO₂/carbonic acid).

Here, the cave below Sphinx gives more credibility to this idea. Possibly the cave is the reason there are no [additional] rooms above. The caves may be one of the reasons why the Great Pyramid was constructed here in the first place.

When humans from Earth go to Mars they will likely settle in/near caves (e.g., lava tubes) too, for the same reason (unfavourable conditions for life on the surface at the time).

Note that the whole structure was probably largely buried in sand for a long time before Egyptians discovered so it was protected at least from some erosion. In any case, the original carving cannot be older than ≈ 37.8 million years (My) and the same should be true for the age of the Great Pyramid.

If the whole structure was originally Egyptian, surely they would fix the proportions by adjusting the body, but perhaps at the time they [re]carved the head they were not even aware there is a body below, as it was buried in sand.

The base may have been uncovered later, perhaps in the reign of Khufu or Khafre when first repairs have been made to the structure.

The Sphinx's body was probably buried in sand for a large part of its history. Various illustrations of the Sphinx done before the 19th century show the head only[77].

Figure 7: The Sphinx as seen by F. L. Norden in 1737

I do not know when the Egyptians started using chimeras in their art, but it's likely not before they found a fossil of a chimera somewhere, if not in the Great Pyramid then perhaps below Sphinx.

Evidence paired with non-polarized minds leads to knowledge of truth, anthropocentric logic leads to religion. That is why for Egyptians these structures were sacred and that is why their origin in time is sacred among Egyptologists.

6.2 Likely origin of mummies, Egyptian gods and the Underworld

If humans were living on Earth during some of the previous extinctions, it should be hard to find evidence. Cultivation of humans on the surface of a planet is unlikely to differ between separate neurogenesis events, so if homo.beta or a similar creature was cultivated more than once, fossilized remains are unlikely to exist or to be found - due to its very short existence on the surface.

The same should be true for any Mars.homo.beta and Venus.homo.beta that visited Earth.

However, by the time these species have visited Earth, they were likely already aware of planetary neurogenesis. So if they are leaving something behind for Earth.homo.beta, it's hard to imagine they wouldn't [try to] leave some image of themselves and/or creatures they are in symbiosis with. Since nothing outlives a fossil, they would probably intentionally fossilize a body and leave it in something extremely durable - like a sturdy granite sarcophagus, in an artificially looking mountain - like a pyramid, so it can be found more easily.

And now one has an excellent candidate for the origin of mummies - the Egyptians seeing a well-preserved body in the sarcophagus was likely the moment when their religion started. From that point on, they would imitate it all - the preservation of the body, the sarcophagus, the pyramid.

And what if that body was a body of homo.gamma? Now one knows the origin of Anubis (homo.gamma.anubis) and other Egyptian gods (note that the other pyramid could have contained the body of homo.gamma.toth, for example).

Most likely, it was not only the body that was fossilized, but the basics of planetary neurogenesis too in some way - now one has the source for the Egyptian Underworld.

Later they've associated the builders with gods, them with stars (such as Sirius). And, since they did not know how big the Earth was or what was its shape, they assumed that stars setting below the horizon were going underground, to the Underworld, only to be reincarnated later.

6.2.1 The non-existing alternative

The origin of Egyptian religion is commonly ignored by Egyptologists, it is simply accepted as is - because it simply cannot be explained under the assumption that Egyptians built all the pyramids.

Before they settled in Egypt, Egyptian ancestors lived west in Sahara for thousands of years until it became a desert (again) some 5000 years ago. There are plenty of remains (like art) that these people left behind, but no pyramids, pharaohs, underworld or gods like Osiris or Anubis. Nothing. Then they settle in Egypt and immediately they have it all. Where does the idea come from?

How does one come up with an idea to build a 150 m tall pyramid out of insanely massive blocks of stone to serve as a grave and a portal to underground for one man or one family?

Sure, Christians are building large buildings (churches and cathedrals) too (which are insanely easier to build and much less massive than a 6 million ton pyramid, even though the technology is much more advanced) but this religion is based on a historical figure. What is this based on? Suppose people would accept building this thing for their pharaoh (one should also ask - how come they have pharaohs now?) but would the pharaoh himself buy this idea - building something that could take decades to finish with a real possibility that you're going to die before it is finished? It's all nonsense unless it was based on something real - something extraordinary they've witnessed, something extraordinary they've found. That was a moment when their religion/government was established. It didn't start out of nothing like we're being forced to accept.

6.2.2 A globalized misinterpretation

Most long-standing religions probably start in one or both of these ways:

- with a [future] shaman/prophet having a vision of something extraordinary, or/and,
- with an encounter of alien or extraordinary phenomena - this may or may not include direct contact, and may include phenomena which over time become well understood (i.e., with the progress of science) or ordinary.

Unfortunately for anyone trying to understand the origins, there are so many different ways for data corruption that any hypotheses on the foundations of an old religion can usually hardly go farther from mere speculation. Misunderstanding and misinterpretation are likely to start already at the source. Even the best or the most credible prophet/shaman is not infallible and is prone to misinterpretation of phenomena, especially if it is a vision of some future event. The vision itself cannot be absolutely accurate and it cannot represent absolute future, rather a possible one, even if it may, in great prophets, represent a highly probable/accurate one. Similar is the case with the encounters of intelligent extra- or intra- terrestrial beings or the artefacts they leave behind. In some cases interpretations may be similar to monkeys interpreting encounters with humans or human technology. And it is not surprising for humans to associate great and inaccessible power with deities. For proudly polarized humans it is hard to accept that some animal more intelligent than a man exists, so anything extraordinary is either automatically absolutely divine (for spiritual homo.beta), or an absolute illusion (for materialistic homo.beta) - which, however, may be acknowledged as divine in order to be exploited (e.g., to control the masses).

Most people are not prophets, genuine truth seekers or truth lovers. They are believers in ideals, who do not understand nor want to understand the truth. This is why religions usually don't last long in their original form, they get so corrupted in parts that they quickly become incoherent and confusing. In the end, they become a perversion someone uses as an excuse to continue chasing ideals that actually represent the inverse of the narrative in the original *truth*.

In some cases, however, the original narrative is better preserved, but it is hardly unambiguous and one must speculate on the nature of that what is preserved - to what degree is it a misinterpretation, a misunderstanding, a vision, an extraordinary encounter, a philosophy?

Consider the Dogon tribe in Africa. Apparently, this tribe possesses a detailed knowledge of the Sirius star system and, although some find it hard to believe it, there is good probability that they knew about the Sirius B (a white dwarf star, invisible to naked eye) - and possibly its orbital period, before this star was discovered by modern astronomy. Allegedly, they even claim there is a 3rd star in the system and a planet. Neither the 3rd star (Sirius C), nor the planet have been discovered so far. The existence of a planet is definitely not ruled out, however if the 3rd star does exist it almost certainly must be in the form of a small brown dwarf with substellar mass. It's hard to even categorize brown dwarfs as stars - they are not massive enough to "ignite" hydrogen fusion and they are best described as something between a Jovian (Jupiter-like) planet and a star (a relative superposition of a star and a planet).

The way Dogons depict the Sirius System is shown in Fig. 8.

Since the 3rd companion star hasn't been found, some argue that the mystery is solved - arrogantly dismissing the possibility of advanced Dogon knowledge, others insist that the 3rd companion still exist in some sense. But why insist on the Dogon interpretation, when it is quite likely that at least some parts are misinterpretation? Note that Dogon information on the orbit of Sirius C is confusing, incoherent and contradictory[78] - strongly going in favour of misinterpretation.

There are viable alternatives. One certainly plausible interpretation is that the image they have of the Sirius System does not represent the current state of the system, rather a past or the future one. The X in the image (assumed to represent Sirius A) might actually represent an explosive event (e.g., a supernova) of which the Sirius B (S2 in the image) represents a leftover mass. Then the sequence of shapes (marked S2 and P) represent the clockwise orbit of the leftover mass. Note that the shape marked P is very similar to S2 and is in the same orbit as S2. Therefore, this might represent a second body (a planet) that was formed in the same event.

According to my theories, it should not be uncommon for the death of a star to produce binary leftovers[1], one of which should be a Jovian planet (or possibly a brown dwarf). The more massive the star the more massive would be the planet. Based on calculations done for the Sun, in case of the Sirius B - with the estimated progenitor mass of $6 M_{\odot}$ [79], the planet should probably have a mass of about 9.33 Jupiter masses (with the uncertainty of $\pm 0.933 M_{\odot}$, not taking into account the uncertainty in the calculations done for the Sun). However, considering the estimated age and nature of the system, it is questionable whether this planet is alive at this point. What may remain is only its own remnant, which

Figure 8: Dogon Sirius System⁶³

could be on the order of the mass of Saturn at most. If it is alive then its orbital period is probably on the order of a year or less, and it is tidally locked to the Sirius B, as large Jovian planets at larger distances appear to have been ruled out[80].

The S3 in the image then, of course, represents Sirius A (rays emanating from this shape may indicate brightness - the only visible star in the system). One problem with this interpretation is that, conventionally, Sirius B should not be a remnant of a supernova explosion (as the expected progenitor mass is insufficient to trigger it). In that case, X on the image might represent the expansion of the star mass (first into a red giant, then a nebula afterwards) - which does not seem convincing. However, conventional assumptions are often wrong and do not predict remnant binaries. A supernova explosion cannot be ruled out, although it probably is unlikely.

The most likely interpretation of X, however, is probably a representation of the orbital coupling of the two newly formed bodies (Sirius B and the planet). It is evident that the X is not drawn as the crossing of two straight lines. One line is significantly curved. This arc probably represents the orbit of a body about Sirius B that is roughly perpendicular to the orbit of Sirius B about the Sirius A. The arc should thus represent the orbit of the leftover planet about Sirius B. Highly inclined orbit may be somewhat unusual for a planet, although not impossible, especially for disturbed systems (Sirius B itself may possess high obliquity relative to its orbit, similar to Uranus). However, such orbit would not be unusual for an artificial satellite. The orbit depicted in the image may thus represent an artificial habitat, perhaps a planned parking orbit of the spaceship that departed for the system from the Solar System. In such case most likely orbit should probably be the habitable zone. In case of Sirius B, this would be an orbit at a distance of about 0.156 AU, with an orbital period of about 22 days. Note that, in the context of long-term survival, the orbit about Sirius B should be preferred over the primary orbit about Sirius A (with the habitable zone about 5 AU), as it should be more stable and would be less exposed to the solar wind from Sirius A, due to the highly eccentric orbit of Sirius B, with the closest distance to Sirius A being about 8.1 AU. As an [older] white dwarf, Sirius B is much less active and cannot emit strong solar winds (due to high surface gravity), so the closer orbital distance is not as dangerous. In fact, older (cooler) white dwarfs which are at a safe distance from other stars regarding the possibility for ignition of type Ia supernovas (or, generally, with no possibility for its mass to exceed the Chandrasekhar mass), are probably the perfect candidates for the set-

tlement of highly advanced civilizations fleeing from less stable systems, such as ours. Sirius B is one such candidate. More massive white dwarfs (such as Sirius B) are also expected to have very strong magnetic fields and these fields could provide additional protection, not only from the solar wind of a companion but from the cosmic mass radiation. The anomalies detected previously in the Sirius System (e.g., controversies regarding colour and gravitational redshift of light) may even be correlated with the activity of advanced intelligence.

Note that the Dogon misinterpretation here is quite understandable and it represents something that could easily happen to modern science in an attempt to decipher alien messages (in fact, with the current state of science, it would probably be much worse). I can see why one would assume that the X represents Sirius A - this makes the orbital eccentricity of Sirius B in the image very high (as it currently is in reality), however, the original eccentricity (before the "supernova" event) may have been low (unless the orbital expansion was adiabatic). The presented alternative interpretation does make sense, it doesn't require a 3rd star companion and is in agreement with modern observations. If a Jovian planet or its remnant would be found in orbit about Sirius B, it would represent a solid evidence for the hypothesis. It should be clear, however that, even if there is no 3rd companion at this time, such companion in the past (whether in the form of a star or a planet) cannot be ruled out, as the transformation of the Sirius B progenitor had destabilized the system. A destabilized system (or the expectation of destabilization) would probably trigger migration of any existing advanced civilization, however, this kind of destabilization is conventionally assumed to have occurred more than 100 million years ago. Assuming the Dogon knowledge is in any way associated with extraterrestrials, it would probably have to be correlated with some more recent migration, which, however - along with a more recent destabilization, cannot be ruled out either. In fact, in my other work, I have hypothesized periodic disturbances in the Sirius System[1] (correlated with the colour and the gravitational shift controversies).

Another alternative interpretation of the image is that it represents an Einstein's cross, which typically involves 5 distinct shapes but only 2 real objects. However, this interpretation is unlikely the correct one.

It is certainly interesting that for both, ancient Egyptians and the Dogon tribe (incl. some other tribes), the Sirius [System] is of great importance. For Egyptians, Sirius A represents the the most important goddess, Isis. Her companion is god Osiris (which was probably the most important god to Egyptians) and may be associated with Sirius B (Sirius B is most important to Dogons as well), although Egyptians didn't associate Osiris with this star (this could be a result of misinterpretation on Egyptian part). It cannot be ruled out then that ancient Egyptians knew about Sirius B as well (the Osiris may have been simply associated with another nearby star because Sirius B could not be seen with a naked eye), so both religions may be based on the same source.

It is still possible that Egyptians did associate a certain god or goddess with Sirius B, just not Osiris. A good candidate is the goddess Nephthys (which they do in some cases refer to as invisible[81]), a sister of Isis. In that case, the Anubis probably should be associated with the hypothetical planet in orbit about Sirius B.

Note also that great similarity exists between the primeval gods of Egypt and those of Sumer. This is very odd since any kind of borrowing between the two is considered to be out of the question[82]. Thus, the remaining possibility is they're all based on the same source.

Note, however, while the source may be associated with extraterrestrials, the extensive knowledge of the Sirius System does not imply that these extraterrestrials came from Sirius. It implies either advanced technology or a vision of an advanced shaman/prophet, with the former probably being more likely (although some shaman still probably has been involved in interpretation). Who had this technology? Most likely the same one who built the Great Pyramid. And that one probably represents something evolved from some homo.beta equivalent, possibly on Mars. Now one must ask, if these extraterrestrials didn't come from the Sirius System, why was the knowledge of this system important? Well perhaps this was their next destination. Thus, instead of a civilization from Sirius colonizing Earth, some indigenous (to Solar System) advanced civilization may have left the Solar System for the Sirius System instead. This indeed makes more sense, considering the fact that, apart from the Great Pyramid (and possibly some other structures) there are no other traces of this civilization (although I don't think they had any permanent settlements on Earth's surface anyway, as it's probably not habitable for them). They may have figured out that the Solar System is nearing the end of a 1st order cycle so they decided to leave (possibly with the intention of coming back, after the cataclysm).

As noted before, I have theorized elsewhere that the Solar System experiences periodic disturbances of different order[1]. The 1st order disturbances are cataclysmic on the biggest scale and they should have a period of about 4.5 billion years (or 4.25 billion, with hypothesized time compression). According to my theories, however, this value should be understood as average. Thus, the end of the current 1st order cycle may even be tens of millions of years in the future. However, the end of a 1st order cycle should also be relatively synchronized with the end of a 2nd order cycle, and we probably are currently at or near the end of one such cycle. I suspect that the end of the current 1st order cycle should occur either *now* or some 26 million years in the future. Either the civilization that left for Sirius (assuming this is indeed what happened) knew that the 1st order cycle ends now, or they weren't sure but

didn't want to risk staying. It is my belief that the original purpose of the Great Pyramid was to shield one from cataclysmic events. The Great Pyramid probably could shield one from a 2nd order cataclysm (at least in the short-term), but not from a 1st order one. It is unlikely that everyone left for Sirius and, if those who stayed have survived, they may be associated with UFO/UAP phenomena. Increasing activity of these phenomena on Earth's surface could probably be correlated with the end of the current 2nd order cycle.

6.3 The apex of enlightenment

When expressed as a decimal number, the latitude coordinate of the Great Pyramid in Giza is 29.9791750, a sequence of numbers strikingly similar to the current speed of light (2.99792458×10^8 m/s).

An interesting synchronicity, hard to believe this is not some kind of a meaningful signal, and possibly also intentionally encoded by the builders.

If the builders were, as hypothesized above, members of an advanced civilization, this probably shouldn't be surprising. However, in case of conscious encoding, this requires that their ratio of unit lengths for space and time was equal to ours (m/s). This as well might not be as hard to believe as it seems, given the following should be true according to the planetary neurogenesis theory:

- all terrestrial planets follow a similar development path (albeit with different speeds - inversely proportional to mass) - they are related species,
- people living on these planets are indigenous [large scale] proteins whose evolution is effectively coded - proteins do not differ much between related species.

From that perspective, rather than the equal m/s ratio being a coincidence, a non-equal ratio being a genetic defect (mutation) may be a more plausible consideration.

The allowed difference would be a difference in magnitude of units (keeping ratios equal) - e.g., the constructors of the pyramid might have divided the sphere into 36 degrees rather than 360, so the latitude would be 2.99791750, matching *our* speed of light even better.

After all, the planet they came from is smaller than Earth (almost 10 times in mass, if they came from Mars).

Note 1:

If homo. β evolved on Mars too, other species that have evolved

on Earth must have evolved on Mars too, albeit probably of different scale.

This makes one wonder - are similar but differently scaled species like Carcharodon Carcharias and Carcharodon Megalodon actually the *same* species, but from different planets?

If the constructors of the pyramid were fleeing from destruction on their own planet, most likely they brought some embryos with them (*Noah's ark*). We could thus pinpoint the time of that arrival through sudden spikes and curiosities in fossil record.

For this creature particularly, the time of arrival would have to be ≥ 16 million years ago (Mya), assuming of course the species of Carcharodon Carcharias was brought from Mars and Megalodon evolved on Earth.

Assuming the ratio of Earth's surface area to Mars's surface area is equal to the ratio of sizes between species, the ratio is:

$$\frac{4\pi R_m^2}{4\pi R_e^2} = \frac{R_m^2}{R_e^2} = \frac{3389.5^2}{6371^2} = 0.283$$

R_m = volumetric mean radius of Mars [km]

R_e = volumetric mean radius of Earth [km]

Assuming the average size of Carcharias 4.23 m and 6.1 m maximum, this gives 14.9 m average and 21.5 maximum for the Megalodon, agreeing well with estimates one can derive from the fossil record.

The same ratio should be valid for homo species. Assuming 1.74 m for the average height of Earth.homo. β , the average height of Mars.homo. β should be:

$$1.74 m \times 0.283 = 0.49242 m \approx 0.5 m$$

Mars.homo.sapiens, being the result of β fusion, should be roughly twice the height of Mars.homo. β , ≈ 1 m.

This size agrees completely with the most reliable[83] eyewitness reports[84] of grey aliens. Now note that passages in the Great Pyramid are about 1.2 m in height - clearly not designed for Earth's humans, but both Martian β and sapiens could easily walk through them.

Using the same ratio one obtains the average height of future Earth.homo.sapiens, 3.5 m.

Note that Venus.homo.sapiens should be roughly the same size as Earth.homo.sapiens. Bones of giant humans 3.5 m tall, have been possibly discovered on Earth[85]. This would probably have to be a Venus.homo.sapiens. The fact that such bones were discovered only in one or two locations in France in limited number strongly suggests that this is not the ancestor of Earth.homo. β , going in favour of the hypothesis.

Note also that, even though human evolution is generally progressive, it has to oscillate (e.g., Neanderthals were bigger and had bigger brains

than modern human, even modern human had a bigger brain 30000 years ago), it is thus possible that human size will temporarily increase to even larger heights before it settles on 3.5 m.

"A vidjesmo ondje i divove, sinove Anakove, koji potječu od divova: sami sebi izgledali smo kao skakavci, a takvi bijasmo i u njihovim očima."

Numbers 13:33

Continuing from the same perspective, assuming there were no defects, why is the encoded speed of light slightly smaller than *ours* ?

In CR there are no absolute constants, and the speed of light is no exception. Thus, this could be the speed of light at the time the pyramid was built. Alternatively, instead of pyramid building time, it might be encoding some other important event in the past, while the pyramid may have been built more recently.

Distance of Earth from the Sun is currently increasing (at the rate $v_r = +15 \pm 4$ cm per year[86], according to the conclusion from one analysis in 2004.). The reason probably lies in the loss of Sun's mass over time and tidal interactions between Earth and the Sun.

However, the local gravitational *constant* G is probably still increasing - a consequence of exchange of electro-magnetic potential for gravitational, as per the hypothesis on the formation of the Solar System and evidence provided in *The Solar System: Nature and Mechanics*. Per the corollary in deduction of mass-charge equation in chapter *Electric polarization and charge/mass exchange* in CR, with the exchange of charge for mass inflation, increase of G must be proportional to the decrease of ϵ property (permittivity, or dielectric constant) of local space. The speed of light thus must be higher now than it was at the time (t_p) encoded in the pyramid:

$$c = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\epsilon\mu}}, \quad c_p = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\epsilon_p\mu}} \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{c_p}{c} = \frac{2.99791750 \times 10^8}{2.99792458 \times 10^8} = \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon\mu}{\epsilon_p\mu}} = \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_p}}$$

$$\frac{\epsilon_p}{\epsilon} = \frac{c^2}{c_p^2} = 1.0000047232843200010504019129459 \quad (1.2)$$

Note that magnetic permeability of space (μ) does not change because its equivalent ($G/c^2 = G_p/c_p^2$) in the spin gravitational vector[87] (S)

does not change.

$$\epsilon = \Delta\epsilon \epsilon_p = \frac{1}{\Delta G} \epsilon_p = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_p^2}{c_1^2}}} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v_p^2}{c_1^2}} \epsilon_p$$

$$G_p = \frac{G}{\Delta G} = G \Delta\epsilon$$

$$M_p = \frac{M}{\Delta\epsilon}$$

$$c_1 = \sqrt{\frac{GM}{R_\odot}}$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{GM}{rc_1^2}}} \sqrt{1 - \frac{G_p M_p}{r_p c_1^2}} \epsilon_p = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{GM}{rc_1^2}}} \sqrt{1 - \frac{GM}{r_p c_1^2}} \epsilon_p$$

c , ϵ = current vacuum speed of light and dielectric *constant* for U_0 scale,
respectively

c_p , ϵ_p = vacuum speed of light and dielectric *constant* for U_0 scale at t_p ,
respectively

G = current gravitational *constant* = 6.674×10^{-11} m³/kgs²

G_p , M_p = gravitational *constant* and Sun's mass, respectively, at t_p

c_1 = space (Keplerian) angular velocity of the 1 R_\odot Sun discontinuity
(presumably occupied by a large scale graviton)

M = total mass of the Sun = 1.988500×10^{30} kg

R_\odot = radius of the Sun = 695700000 m

r , r_p = current (149.598×10^9 m) orbital radius of Earth, and orbital radius
at t_p , respectively

For the details on the used ΔG relation (changes in gravitational constant) here, see the Solar System analysis (chapter *Evidence for a constant change of G*[88]). In short, the local gravitational constant G changes depending on the distance of the Earth from the large scale gravitons of the Sun with which the Earth graviton(s) is(are) entangled with. Yearly oscillation of the G constant is correlated with the 2 inner Sun gravitons (discontinuities), however, long-term changes in orbital distance are correlated with the outer graviton (1 R_\odot discontinuity).

From the above, one can deduce r_p :

$$r_p = \frac{GM}{c_1^2} \frac{1}{1 - (1 - \frac{GM}{rc_1^2}) \frac{\epsilon^2}{\epsilon_p^2}} = R_\odot \frac{1}{1 - (1 - \frac{R_\odot}{r}) \frac{\epsilon^2}{\epsilon_p^2}} = 149.296 \times 10^9 \text{ m} \quad (1.3)$$

and now get the time passed since the encoded event:

$$\Delta t_p = (r - r_p) \frac{1}{v_r} = 2013_{-424}^{+732} \text{ My} \quad (1.4)$$

Large uncertainties are due to the uncertainty in v_r (0.15 ± 0.04 m/y), uncertainties in r and r_p are assumed to be equal.

However, the used value for v_r may not be correct (as an average value), a proper value for v_r may be obtained with the assumption that lunar orbital recession is equal in nature to Earth's recession from the Sun:

A valid assumption, considering that the Moon's orbit about Earth seems to be entangled with the orbit of Mars about the Sun - the nature of this entanglement will change only once the Moon's graviton collapses into Earth. This may or may not be inconsistent with fossil records[89] (I haven't checked), but interpretations of these records assume Earth did not have other moons or that the current Moon did not significantly change mass over time - an assumption which may not be true and can lead to more inconsistencies considering fossil records from different ages.

$$\frac{dr}{dt} v_{rm} = \frac{dr_m}{dt_m} v_r$$

$$\frac{dr}{dr_m} = \frac{r}{r_m}$$

$$\frac{dt_m}{dt} = \frac{2\pi r_c}{v_c} \frac{v_s}{2\pi r_s} = \frac{r_c v_s}{v_c r_s}$$

$$v_r = \frac{r}{r_m} \frac{dt_m}{dt} v_{rm} = 0.620114 \pm 0.000004 \frac{m}{y}$$

r = Earth's distance from the Sun = 149.6×10^9 m

r_m = Moon's distance from the Earth = 0.3844×10^9 m

r_c = radius of the Earth's inner large scale graviton (\approx inner core radius) =
1206115 m

v_c = space (Keplerian) angular velocity of the Earth's inner discontinuity =
18175.480768 m/s

r_s = radius of the Sun's outer large scale graviton (\approx surface discontinuity) =
695700000 m

$$v_s = \text{space (Keplerian) angular velocity of the Sun's outer discontinuity} = 436762.051408 \text{ m/s}$$

where $v_{r_m} = +38.247 \pm 0.004 \text{ mm/y} = +0.038247 \pm 0.000004 \text{ m/y}$ is the orbital recession of the Moon relative to Earth.

Similar to the Earth's graviton entanglement with the Sun's outer graviton, here it is assumed that the Moon's graviton is entangled with the Earth's major graviton.

Note that the space (Keplerian) angular velocity is the velocity with the total mass of the body coupled to the graviton, not just the mass *below* the graviton radius. This velocity would thus be equal to the classical Keplerian velocity at the graviton radius if all mass would be concentrated at/below the graviton radius (I have hypothesized elsewhere that this has even been the case initially). Since the graviton is coupled to total mass, not solely to the mass below the radius, the calculation is equivalent. Thus, the velocity v_c , for example, is equal to:

$$v_c = \sqrt{\frac{GM}{r_c}}$$

$$M = \text{total mass of the Earth} = 5.97 \times 10^{24} \text{ kg}$$

Obtained v_r agrees very well with measurements taken by radar observations (ranging) and landers in the period 1961. - 1997. ($0.61 \pm 0.06 \text{ m/y}$)[86], so this indeed may be the proper rate of Earth's orbital recession (or at least closer to the average).

With updated v_r :

$$\Delta t_p = (r - r_p) \frac{1}{v_r} = 486774105^{+3k}_{-3k} \text{ years}$$

A very interesting result, due to the following:

- the time is in agreement with the Cambrian-Ordovician extinction (currently estimated at $485.4 \pm 1.9 \text{ Mya}$ [90]),
- in some literature, the upper Cambrian boundary of 486.8 Mya is stated[91], basically equal to the obtained value,
- the following period is characterized by intense diversification of marine animal life (known as Ordovician radiation),
- appearance of new life habits and habitats, and
- first appearance of land plants.

Note 1: Time t_p is not corrected for the hypothesized time compression during strong evolution events, but neither are the Cambrian-Ordovician extinction estimates, so in this context, adjustment ($\approx -10\text{my}$) is irrelevant.

Note 2: Apparently, there are claims associating certain fossil records with advanced civilizations (including alleged human shoe prints from the Ordovician period), but I have not seen convincing evidence nor serious research regarding these claims, either to confirm or refute the hypothesis.

Sadly, what I did saw, regarding such claims, was the competition to sustain or prove the dogmatic viewpoints of two opposing sides. None of them did rise above the ego-centric standpoint to even consider humans from another planet.

Note 3: Could the coded time also represent the age the pyramid was built originally? That's highly unlikely, if not impossible, for various reasons, e.g., tectonic plate movement, estimated age of the underlying bedrock, estimated age of rocks used in construction, erosion. If the builders did construct the pyramid as a signal to us, they must have known, at least approximately, at what time humans would evolve on the planet and be able to decode it. With such knowledge, they would've surely accounted for the movement of plates too (assuming the signal was consciously constructed). However, with such a long period, uncertainty would probably be significant (regardless of how advanced the builders are), and other issues probably rule out this age as the age of the pyramid construction. But the *choice* of the coded event is, nonetheless interesting. As I have hypothesized, extinction events are highly correlated with planetary neurogenesis events, thus, apart from the pyramidal shape and size, this is something else that can be correlated with neurogenesis. The encoded age could represent the age of the start of the Earth's neurogenesis.

Note that the location of the pyramid is unlikely a meaningless coincidence either - the area is the geographical centre of [all land surfaces on] Earth. Initially, it was calculated that the Great Pyramid is at the actual location of the centre and that it was likely to be the "last of the present land surface of the earth" to survive a cataclysmic event, due to its positioning[92]. This goes in favour of the hypothesis that it was built to survive the cataclysmic events of neurogenesis.

More recent calculations put the geographical centre north of Giza, in Turkey. However, this does not rule out that Giza was the centre at the time of construction or that the imprecise centring was intentional in order to encode the proper speed of light.

In case of neurogenesis, however, where the cells are transferred to the poles, it is the latitudinal location that matters. Here, the Great Pyramid is probably in the optimal position, perhaps not even due to the fact that

a meridian crossing the Great Pyramid would pass over more land than at any other location on Earth, but because it is likely the position where the magnetic field strength of the collapsing graviton(s) would be minimal. The position of Moon's graviton absorption should be the position of planet's magnetic field strength minimum. This position can be determined - Moon's inclination of 28.58° to Earth's equator should be the latitude of impact (Moon graviton absorption) on Earth.

This can be either south or north of the equator. If it impacts south hemisphere, the safest location is thus 28.58° north of equator on the opposite side of Earth. The location of the Great Pyramid is $29^\circ 58'$ (29.98°) N. A remarkable agreement. Small correction, if necessary, ($29.98 - 28.58 = 1.4^\circ$) could come from changes in Moon's obliquity (1.54° to ecliptic, 6.68° to orbit). But again, small deviation does not make a large difference in security and was perhaps intentional in order to encode the speed of light precisely.

Note that there exists a peculiar quadratic structure on Mars[93] exactly at 28.58° N[94]. Therefore, these are probably the remains of a structure that was built for the same purpose as the Great Pyramid on Earth.

Also note that Valles Marineris on Mars is south of the equator, going in favour of the hypothesis. The inclination of Phobos/Deimos of 1° doesn't seem to correspond to the latitude of rifts of Valles Marineris (largest rift is centred at $\approx 10^\circ$ S, while the middle of all 3 rifts is at $\approx 6.6^\circ$), however, these rifts correspond to embryonic neurogenesis, while Phobos/Deimos are likely the remains of a moon created for adult neurogenesis. Indeed, there is a small rift north of, and parallel to, these 3 rifts, located at 1° S, equal to Phobos/Deimos inclination. Dating of the rifts and Phobos/Deimos should provide clues on the end of embryonic neurogenesis and start/end of adult neurogenesis on Mars. Note that a moon's inclination to planet's equator is generally the maximum possible latitude of impact (in case the prevailing force is gravity) so there are some requirements for impact latitude to actually be maximal (equal to inclination). In case of homogeneous distribution of gravity, the impact latitude is determined by electro-magnetic forces (especially if the collapsing graviton is strongly charged, two-dimensional).

Thus, the magnetic poles must be asymmetric in strength and/or position and the magnitude of asymmetry should correspond to moon's orbital inclination.

Since Earth's magnetic poles are of similar strength, the asymmetry must be in position.

Current position of Earth's magnetic poles is indeed asymmetric and corresponds very well to Moon's orbital inclination - the *deepest* point of South Atlantic Anomaly (SAA), weakest magnetic field on Earth, is roughly at 26° S[95]. It is also moving westward, away from Giza.

While Earth's north magnetic pole is increasing its alignment with geo-

graphic north pole, the south magnetic pole is slowly moving northwards from the south pole (it's currently at 64° S latitude). Both poles are decreasing eastern longitude, but south pole's is decreasing much more slowly, so they are likely aligning longitude, which should happen in year ≈ 2026 according to current models[96].

Note that SAA is highly correlated with two poles:

- it is moving in the same direction,
- it is exactly at the opposite side of Earth,
- it's deflection from the equator (26°) is equal to the south magnetic pole's deflection from the geographic south pole.

The SAA is currently 90° away from Giza, thus, it should move for additional 90° before the impact. At current rate ($\approx 0.3^\circ/\text{year}$) this would take 300 years, however, it is unlikely for the rate to remain constant. The SAA is apparently splitting into two poles moving in opposite directions (the *main*, stronger, pole is moving westward). Sudden acceleration is possible once these separate, which could coincide with longitudinal alignment of magnetic poles.

But is the used value for recession speed the correct value for the average? Although the recession cannot be linear, significant changes are expected only near the points of strong evolution. However, as I have hypothesized, the Solar System should actually be near such point. The obtained and calculated values suggest that Earth's orbital recession is slowing down.

The slowdown of Earth's recession can be further confirmed with the calculation of the actual average rate of recession. I have previously established that Earth has, since formation, moved from ≈ 0.63 MAU to ≈ 0.66 MAU[97], where MAU is the Sun-Mars distance.

Assuming this is correct, one can obtain the average rate:

$$v_{avg} = \left(\frac{r}{r_M} - \frac{R_i}{R_\odot} \right) \frac{r_M}{\Delta T_{E_{img}}}$$

$$v_r = v_{avg} = (0.656370656370 - 0.633584158866) \frac{r_M}{\Delta T_{E_{img}}}$$

$$= 1.143942403367^{+0.013}_{-0.013} \frac{m}{y}$$

r = Earth's distance from the Sun = 149.6×10^9 m

r_M = Mars' distance from the Sun = 227.92×10^9 m

R_i = 440784499.323 m = initial radius of the Earth's major graviton[98], fossilized as the Sun's 2/3 R_\odot discontinuity

R_\odot = radius of the Sun = 695700000 m

$\Delta T_{E_{img}}$ = estimated age of Earth = img age of Earth = $4.54 \pm 0.05 \times 10^9$ years

The calculated average is higher than the one obtained from the recent measurements, agreeing with the hypothesis.

This gives:

$$\Delta t_p = (r - r_p) \frac{1}{v_r} = 263872933 \begin{smallmatrix} +3m \\ -3m \end{smallmatrix} \text{ years}$$

Of course, there was a large extinction 260 Mya (End-Capitanian), which was likely the result of splitting of the major energy level - second extinction being the Permian-Triassic event 252 Mya (major mass extinction). Note the significance of error margins, if one uses 0.63/0.66 MAU:

$$v_r = v_{r_{avg}} = (0.66 - 0.63) \frac{r_M}{\Delta T_{E_{img}}} = 1.506 \frac{m}{y}$$

giving:

$$\Delta t_p = (r - r_p) \frac{1}{v_r} = 200435217 \text{ years}$$

A difference of roughly 60 My compared to previous result. However, again, a major mass extinction occurred 201 Mya (Triassic-Jurassic) as well, so if the coded event has to be associated with mass extinctions - as calculations suggest, even with large uncertainties, it would likely be one of these two as there are no major extinctions in between, only one larger extinction event at 230 Mya (Carnian Pluvial event), characterized by the first appearance of dinosaurs (~230 Mya). Note that the actual period may be 0.63 - 0.66, the period 0.656370656370 - 0.633584158866 should be understood as the period during which the v_r did not change significantly, it doesn't include the compression of time at the start and the end of the period. Note also that the bunch of numbers in the values above should not be interpreted as high precision, the actual precision is lower, however, I did not bother rounding the numbers as this version of the paper may not be final.

The measurements do suggest that the recession is slowing - the obtained rate is decreasing proportionally to time and inversely proportionally to the period of a set of measurements, as shown in Table 3.

data set	method	period	v_r [cm/y]
0	calculated average	4.54 Ga - present	110 - 150
1	ranging + landers	1961 - 1997	61.0 ±6.0 ^a
1	landers	1971 - 1997	21.3 ±5.6 ^a
2	ranging + orbiters	1961 - 2003	14.4 ±1.2 ^a
2	landers + orbiters	1971 - 2003	9.7 ±0.3 ^a

Table 3: Earth's orbital recession rate over time, sources: a⁸⁶

Note that the slowdown is good evidence for the 4.5i (4.25) billion years Solar System cycle.

Although the data suggests overall decreasing magnitude, the decrease should also oscillate, having the form of general scalar oscillation in CR, which, taking into account the 1st and 2nd order (scale) only, is:

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = v_r = A \sin \left(\frac{(r + \phi_1)/MAU - 0.63}{0.69 - 0.63} 2\pi \right) \left[1 + B \sin \left(\frac{(r + \phi_2)/MAU - 0.63}{0.69 - 0.63} 2\pi f \right) \right]$$

$$A = v_{r_{avg}} \times \frac{\pi}{2}$$

$$0.63 \text{ MAU} \leq r \leq 0.69 \text{ MAU}$$

A = amplitude of the 1st order oscillation (4.5 Gy cycle)

B = amplitude of the 2nd order oscillation (yearly)

ϕ_1 = phase shift of the 1st order oscillation

ϕ_2 = phase shift of the 2nd order oscillation

f = frequency of the 2nd order oscillation

First term here [A sin()] is due to the change in the gravitational *constant* (G) as part of the 4.5 Gy cycle, while the second term [B sin()] is due to orbital eccentricity as part of the annual G oscillation.

I have previously calculated (in the analysis of the Solar System) the amplitude and phase shift of yearly G oscillation. This oscillation is small and orbital eccentricity has surely been taken into account in the analysis of measurements so the 2nd term of the equation can be discarded.

There is a possibility that the 2nd order oscillation has a different source and yearly G change is the 3rd order oscillation but I do not see what could be the cause of it.

Calculated $v_{r_{avg}} = 1.143942403367 \text{ m/y}$ gives results in good agreement with the calculated current v_r (0.62 m/y) and measurements of a set 1 performed 1961. - 1997. (ranging + landers). For $\phi_1 = 0$ and $r = 0.656370656370 \text{ MAU}$ (current Earth-Sun distance), the equation gives:

$$v_r = 0.6666 \frac{m}{y}$$

Phase shift of 0 is unlikely though, a small ϕ_1 (0.00025 MAU) would decrease v_r to the previously calculated value (0.62 m/y). Source code:(Fig.: recess_osc.php +) Note that, with v_r decreasing at the predicted rate it would take almost 3.2 billion years to reach 0:

$$t = \int dt = \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \frac{1}{v_r} dr$$

using substitution (making integration non-dimensional):

$$x = \frac{r + \phi_1}{MAU}$$

$$x_1 = \frac{r_1 + \phi_1}{MAU}, \quad x_2 = \frac{r_2 + \phi_1}{MAU}$$

$$A = v_{avg} \times \frac{\pi}{2} \times \frac{1}{MAU}$$

$$u = \frac{x - 0.63}{0.69 - 0.63} 2\pi$$

$$u_1 = \frac{x_1 - 0.63}{0.69 - 0.63} 2\pi, \quad u_2 = \frac{x_2 - 0.63}{0.69 - 0.63} 2\pi$$

$$du = \frac{2\pi}{0.69 - 0.63} dx$$

one gets the simplified equation for time t:

$$t = \frac{1}{A} \int_{u_1}^{u_2} \frac{1}{\sin(u)} \frac{0.69 - 0.63}{2\pi} du$$

$$t = \frac{1}{A} \frac{0.06}{2\pi} \left(\ln \left| \tan \frac{u_2}{2} \right| - \ln \left| \tan \frac{u_1}{2} \right| \right)$$

giving the solution:

$$t = t_{img} = 3166701318.5 \text{ img years} = 3.1667013185 \times 10^9 y_i$$

$$r_1 = 0.656370656370 \text{ MAU}$$

$$r_2 = 0.66 \text{ MAU}$$

$$\text{MAU} = 227.92 \times 10^9 \text{ m}$$

$$\phi_1 = 0.00025 \text{ MAU}$$

This is because the above equations are not time dependent ($dv/dt = 0$), they are only space dependent ($dv/dr \ll 0$).

However, one must take into account the compression of time at the end of the cycle (this is obvious from another angle - if the cycle is 4.25 Gy long and ≈ 4.25 Gy has already passed, the time left must be much shorter, note also that the phase shift is required - ϕ_1 of 0 gives infinity for t), when the quantum of time Δt will decrease in scale.

With the compression, v_r in the same reference frame will be effectively increasing.

As I have previously calculated (see *The Solar System: Nature and Mechanics*), for the 4.25 (4.54 unadjusted) Gy 1st order cycle, the compression of time is 69573495.04 years. Now, assuming that the above used unit y_i represents the uncompressed period equal to one orbital period per the 1st order compression:

$$y_i = \frac{1}{\Delta t_{c_u}} y^2 = \frac{1}{69573495.04} y$$

How much [real] time is left one can now obtain simply by the following equation:

$$t = t_{re} = 46 y$$

Giving the following year for the end of the cycle (assuming Earth was at the distance r_1 in year 2020):

$$t_{END} = 2020 + 46 = 2066$$

However, the validity of the above assumptions is very questionable.

Certainly, the initially obtained value of 2 billion years ago for the coded event would also be very interesting, due to the following:

- 2 billion years ago was the time of the greatest extinction event on Earth[99],
- Venus was habitable[100] at the time,
- analysis of rocks in Gale crater by Curiosity suggests water flowed there 2 Gya,
- a natural (or not?) nuclear fission reactor[101] was also operating at the time, in Africa.

Note that the extinction event on Earth 2 billion years ago is not associated with neurogenesis on Earth (possibly with the creation of the mantle/core boundary), but neurogenesis extinction event could have been happening on Venus or Mars at the time.

In any case, one could not attribute species like Carcharodon Carcharias to any visitors at this time, but one cannot rule out more recent visitors (e.g., Mars.homo.sapiens) indulging into the realization of such fun hypothesis.

Recent analyses of Martian meteorites suggest that a significant part of Mars' crust is much younger than previously thought[102], less than 200 million years. More recent research has yielded evidence for even more

recent geological activity[103] (youngest, $\approx 50\,000$ years ago) showing that Mars is still volcanically active.

Of course, embryonic neurogenesis on Mars likely ended some 850 million years after its formation, but this could be interpreted as evidence of hypothesized shorter adult neurogenesis events.

I believe, however, that during the recent activity (50 000 years ago) Mars was not habitable (not even partially), this was rather a precursor of upcoming events and increasing habitability (as habitability on Earth decreases, on Mars it should be increasing, at least partially).

If Carcharias was brought from Mars, it may have been *brought* from mantle layers, not the surface. This may be plausible - CSF fluids in the mantle are oceans which are, during neurogenesis, at times replenished with surface water. Note that this also implies that Megalodon could still be living in an ocean within the mantle of Earth.

However, these animals cannot be exactly the same, they must have some specific adaptations due to a difference in pH between (current) surface and mantle oceans (I assume the pressure/temperature in the living cells and oceans of the mantle is maintained similar to current conditions on the surface, pH being the main difference).

Note that introduction of *alien* species to Earth does not imply physical transfer of developed bodies, in general, this is likely the transfer of genetic material. Homo.sapiens should even be advanced enough to be able to synthesize DNA so the transfer may not be limited to extant species.

UPDATE 2022.05.12

Analysis of rocks in Utopia Planitia shows liquid water existed there ≈ 700 million years ago (the age is, however, based on crater counting statistics - which depends on the cratering rate, which, for Mars, is uncertain).

Regardless of the potential heat source, the in situ observations manifest recent aqueous activities on Mars, suggesting that the cold and dry late Amazonian epoch may have been episodically punctuated by short-duration climatic warming events that result in melting of ground ice at latitude less than 30°N . [104]

Episodic habitability is exactly what is predicted by the hypothesis of adult neurogenesis, so this is another evidence in its favour.

I will not delve into how plausible are spontaneous nuclear fission reactions occurring on the same continent at the same time, but could pyramids and Sphinx survive millions of years?

There are natural formations on Earth, such as mountains, billions of years old, and these buildings are effectively carved out mountains, especially Sphinx. The Great Pyramid probably also had some durable protective layer until it decayed or someone used it some time ago.

However, the analysis of bedrock and stones used in construction rules out ages bigger than ≈ 37.8 million years. Erosion puts additional constraints but it depends on what the original casing was made of and how thick it was. In any case, dating of casing stones available now will not reveal the date of original construction, more likely a date of repair by someone who worshipped the structure.

I'm sure there were at least two arrivals of homo from two different planets (Mars and Venus), but probably more. Mars.homo and Venus.homo may have even existed at the same time (descendants of one may have built the Khufu pyramid, descendants of the other Khafre).

The current assumption among researchers is that the rock used in the construction of pyramids came from nearby sites (i.e., Mokattam) and thus was formed during Eocene epoch which lasted from 56 - 33.9 million years ago.

All things considered, none of the above calculated ages can be the age of construction, but they do seem to be highly correlated with planetary neurogenesis. The encoded value can also be interpreted as a signal telling us that the speed of light is not constant. If it was important [to god?] for the pyramids to remain preserved (and it seems it was) the maintenance could have even been done by multiple species over time (e.g., Mars.homo.sapiens), not just by Egyptians.

The two pyramids were built using limestone and granite. Radioisotope dating can be used to date older sedimentary rocks (e.g., limestone) only indirectly, but not once they have been removed from the site of formation. As far as I am aware, no radioisotope dating has been performed on granite rocks inside the two pyramids. But this wouldn't be much useful either, it could only discard construction ages older than the granite. Luminescence dating (optical/thermo) can be used to establish the last time of exposure to sunlight or intense heat of minerals present in both, limestone and granite. This dating technique can provide correct dates only for samples up to a 0.5 - 1 million years *old* (non-exposure time), depending on conditions.

However, it would be useful in this case too, if not for absolute dating (assuming construction indeed occurred more than million years ago) but to confirm or refute the hypothesis on builders - if the pyramid was constructed more than a million years ago the sample would be saturated, confirming it was not constructed by Egyptians. To my knowledge, this method has not been used to

date the construction of the two pyramids explicitly. The closest monument on which dating was attempted using the method was the Valley Temple of Khafre (Chephren)[105]. Interestingly, it is claimed that the sample was nearly saturated (no attempt to calculate the age was made, but from the data they provided the age of about 29250 years can be obtained), but the researchers assumed the sample was taken from a cut too deep into the rock (farther than the light can penetrate, i.e. typically more than 4-5 mm, but can be 10 mm or more) and the obtained age was dismissed as non-indicative of the age of construction (it was rather interpreted as geological). However, additional sampling and analysis have been done later[106], obtaining ages 3000 ± 420 BC and 1050 ± 540 BC for the Valley Temple. The first date may be interpreted as the date of construction, but the second date proves Egyptians did maintenance work on Giza monuments and it would be necessary to analyse multiple samples from various parts of the structure in order to obtain the date of original construction.

Due to nature of cults, however, one has to question whether the choice of samples was biased or not. It is still very much possible that both of the obtained dates represent maintenance dates.

External casing of Menkaure (Mykerinus) pyramid has also been dated, confirming Egyptians were involved, at least in maintenance.

The choice of Menkaure here raises some suspicion. Why Menkaure and not the two bigger pyramids? Maybe they did take samples from them all but chose not to publish the results from the other two? Were they, maybe, not allowed to take samples from the other two because the associated cult was afraid of the results? Interesting also is the choice of samples in the dating of Menkaure. The sampling was limited to the outer casing of the pyramid, near the base - exactly where the most maintenance is expected (especially if the pyramid was exposed to flooding, which is possible if it was built when the sea levels were higher or the elevation of the area was lower).

Some protective casing and repairs have also been done by Egyptians on the other two greatest pyramids on Giza plateau. They did such works on Sphinx as well. That all the Egyptians did were repairs, not the original construction, can easily be confirmed even without the proper luminescence dating - by the proper analysis of the already performed radiocarbon dating[107].

However, it would be nice to know the ages of construction at least roughly, which can only be revealed using luminescence dating on the stones within the two great pyramids - this has not been done.

6.3.1 The alternative in light

Here I will exercise alternative interpretations of the correlation between the Great Pyramid location and the speed of light.

If one assumes that building material for the pyramids came from nearby locations, and assuming the construction is correlated with extinctions, the most likely date of construction should probably be the time of the last larger extinction, about 37.8 Ma (Mid-Late Eocene) or perhaps some smaller more recent one.

The location of the pyramid on the globe changes with continental drifts (although, is it possible that over large timescales the current position is the average?).

There are two major forces affecting the African plate and the Pyramids - spreading of the sea floor from the Mid-Atlantic Ridge and Central Indian Ridge (CIR)[108]. The CIR is younger (interestingly, it opened some 38 Mya, corresponding to Mid-Late Eocene extinction) and spreading a bit faster. One interesting interpretation for the appearance of CIR would thus be the stabilization of the African plate.

One source from 1997. indicates that African plate is moving northwards 2.15 cm per year[109]. One might assume the builders, taking this movement into account, wanted to ensure that the location of the pyramid was synchronized with *our* speed of light at *our* Judgement day.

If one approximates 1° latitude with 111.111 km, the location of the pyramid will then match the speed of light in:

$$[(29.9792458^\circ - 29.9791750^\circ) \times 111111 \text{ m}/^\circ] \times \frac{1}{0.0215 \text{ m/year}} = 365.89 \approx 366 \text{ years}$$

Interesting result because it closely matches the number of days in 1 year, could be interpreted as a signal on relativity in periods such as days and years (as exercised previously in this paper) .

The result agrees well with the previous hypothesis on the Judgement day occurring this century - with the pulse of strong evolution taken into account, when the movement of the African plate should briefly accelerate, the interval of 366 years vanishes in decades (the 366 years / 366 days correlation may now be interpreted as a signal that the interval gets compressed).

All generally weakly evolving processes should accelerate during strong evolution. I have previously concluded that anthropogenic CO₂ will not be sufficient to increase acidity of oceans in order to reach the required pH level for neurogenesis. Thus, one can expect significant increase in activity at mid-oceanic ridges. This will accelerate the movement of

plates.

Assuming the plate movement will, overall, follow the previously derived equation for the speed of evolution (currently correlated with atmospheric CO₂):

$$T_{1/2} = 2C_1 - \frac{C_1}{CO_2(T_1)} \times CO_2 = 2C_1 - \frac{C_1}{CO_2(T_1)} \times 300 \times \left(\frac{6}{5} \times 2^{45x^2}\right)^x \quad (1.5)$$

$$x = \frac{T - 1905}{10 \times 55} = \frac{T - 1905}{550}$$

, and assuming the location of the Great Pyramid was 29.9791750° in 1997., these 366 *years* will vanish in year (T):

$$T_{1/2} = 2 \times 366 - \frac{366}{357.9} \times 300 \times \left(\frac{6}{5} \times 2^{45x^2}\right)^x = 0$$

$$T = 2068$$

C₁ = vanishing interval = 366 years

T₁ = initial year = 1997

CO₂(T₁) = atm. concentration of CO₂ at T₁ = 357.9 ppmv

Again, the result is interesting...

What about uncertainty?

The most questionable parameter here is the choice of the initial year. It should probably be less than 1997, however, change in the initial year causes only ≈ 1/4 - 1/3 of that change in the outcome. In example, choosing year 1990 for the initial year gives year 2066 (only 2 years difference).

Another possibility is that the location is to be synchronized with the speed of light as it was at the time of construction.

Using equations 1.2 - 1.4, with Δt_p = 37.8 × 10⁶ y, one obtains the speed of light at this time:

$$c_p = 2.99792403 \times 10^8 \frac{m}{s}$$

The location of the pyramid will match this speed in:

$$[(29.9792403^\circ - 29.9791750^\circ) \times 1111111 \text{ m}/^\circ] \times \frac{1}{0.0215 \text{ m}/y} = 337.47 \approx 337 \text{ years}$$

Using equation 1.5 and initial year 1997 one, of course, obtains the same outcome (the outcome is sensitive to initial year, not much on C₁) - year 2068 (or 2066 for initial year 1990).

Now, let's suppose the location and the speed of light (at construction) synchronizing in year 2066. The speed of light is:

$$\begin{aligned} & [(2066 - 2020) y \times 0.0215 m/y \times \frac{1}{111111 m/^\circ} + 29.9791750^\circ] \times 10^7 m/s^\circ \\ & = 2.99791839 \times 10^8 \frac{m}{s} \end{aligned}$$

From this, one obtains this age:

$$\Delta t_p = 424.7 Ma$$

This could be correlated with Lau/Mulde events and global drop in sea level, in Silurian. Again, unlikely as the construction date, however, perhaps a signal pointing to the Silurian hypothesis?

6.4 Strong clues in the structure of the Great (Khufu) Pyramid

It has been noted before that passages in the Great Pyramid are 1.2 m in height and that Mars.homo.sapiens should be about 1 m in height. Since Mars.homo.sapiens has the same height as the grey aliens (greys) and it has been predicted that sapiens should look exactly like greys[4], the greys probably belong to the Mars.homo.sapiens species. The hypothesis of planetary neurogenesis also predicts that homo.sapiens individuals represent components (probably large scale proteins) of planet's neuron cells. Since the equivalent of cell's cytoplasm on large scale is freshwater, these beings are probably either aquatic or amphibian. Now take a look at the diagram of the interior structures in the Great Pyramid, shown in Fig. 9.

From the diagram it can be clearly seen which passages are the original structures and which have been created at a later time by someone with far less advanced technology. One low-tech passage is the Robber's Tunnel (marked by number 2), including the small tunnel around the granite block (red coloured in the diagram) dug in order to access the ascending corridor behind it (marked by number 6). Another such tunnel is probably the vertical tunnel (number 11).

Note that the tunnel 11 is not only irregular (all other original tunnels are straight) but it is not well aligned with the descending tunnel (4) at the bottom, just like the tunnel 2 is not well aligned with the ascending corridor (6). If, however, the original builders had no capability to move the granite block [at the bottom of the ascending corridor] once it was put in place (which should be questionable), they might have dug the tunnel 11 themselves (after the cataclysm?) so they can get out. In any case, given the misalignment in this structure and the level of sophistication in other structures, it seems highly unlikely that this tunnel was a part of the original plan. Perhaps the original builder(s) had no intention

Figure 9: Great Pyramid of Giza, S-N diagram¹¹⁰

to get out and wanted/expected to die inside (which can certainly be reasonable in some contexts), in which case, whoever first penetrated inside afterwards must have found remains of the body/bodies of the builder(s).

The Robber's Tunnel, so called, was probably not cut by some robbers, rather the common Egyptians before they started building their own, much less sophisticated (at least in the start), pyramids, once they saw what was inside this one.

Now, without the tunnels that were probably dug out later (11 and 2), with the air-shafts (10) designed to collect rainwater and with the granite block tightly installed at the bottom of the tunnel 6 (note that all the blocks inside are tightly aligned), the rainwater would accumulate inside and some air would be left trapped in the chambers as well (we're probably talking here about freshwater mammals or mammalian amphibians). Taking into account that pyramidal neuron cells look like, well, pyramids, perhaps the builders were not unconsciously imitating a neuron cell, rather consciously imitating their own natural habitat. Another purpose of the granite block at the bottom was not only to block freshwater getting out but also to block saltwater getting in (as noted before, the pyramid was likely built to withstand cataclysmic events - such as rising sea levels). Such blocks probably exist in their natural habitat, where the external fluid is the CSF, or the salty ocean.

Another evidence going in favour of amphibians is the Sphinx *temple* (it's unlikely that it was a temple, but that's the official name based on the established narrative). It is located next to the Sphinx enclosure but it is on lower elevation. It seems that this structure was intentionally constructed in such way to get flooded, as some have already hypothesized[111].

7 On the observed signals

In the results of calculations above high agreement was obtained with multiple major extinctions across multiple different interpretations, or, input parameters. How to explain this? It is probably unlikely that the builders would consciously encode multiple interpretations. However, this is unlikely a meaningless coincidence either. I believe this encoding is a result of subconscious influence on the builders (it is even possible that the shape and size were not chosen consciously to match a typical Earth's neuron cell). I interpret this as meaningful synchronicity. I have written extensively about synchronicity elsewhere so i won't

go into details here, but I will say that the phenomenon is definitely real and it is something I experience almost on a daily basis, if not daily.

Generally, however, I do not suggest taking signals of synchronicity as overly confident evidence, as the signals are prone to misinterpretation. However, sometimes the potential ambiguity is low, and this is one of such cases. The Great Pyramid seems to be highly correlated with planetary neurogenesis.

8 Confirmation in pyramids?

I have previously calculated potential years of asteroid impacts and massive extinctions[112] on the surface of the Earth.

Multiple indicators can be found in my works, suggesting that the first impact will occur in the year 2029 ($\pm 1-2$ years) - this could be considered the first wave of neurogenesis stimulated migration. Last wave (or beginning of the end of the surface world) may start about the year 2060, as previously hypothesized. This could also be encoded in the pyramids.

Indeed, superimposing the location of Giza pyramids from the perspective of the god Earth to the location of planets in years 2029 (*day 1*) and 2061 (*day 5*), one can see the obvious alignment, shown in Fig. 10.

Figure 10: Correlation of Giza pyramids with inner planets

Not only do pyramids align with the Sun and the planets in these years, they align on my birthday (September 1st) which makes it a very clear signal for me (and may be interpreted as a confirmation that the September 1st is the birthdate of the anti-christ of the current event - as noted before, September 1st occurs after 8 months of a year have passed, and $8 / 12 = 2/3 = 0.666$).

From the alignment, one can even deduce who built the pyramids. Khufu pyramid was built by Mars.homo (or humanoids evolved on Mars) - as hypothesized already, Khafre pyramid by Venus.homo and the Menkaure pyramid

(aligned with the Sun) was built by Egyptians (Earth.homo. β) - revealing that the worshipping of the Sun by the Egyptians was yet another signal. Again, however, since Egyptian religion (but not just Egyptian) is probably based on artefacts left by original builders, this interpretation could be wrong. Perhaps the builders of Menkaure pyramid did come from Earth, but not Earth's surface, rather Earth's subsurface.

In my analysis of the Solar System I have found that the Earth's core and the Sun are highly correlated. Perhaps the Sun here then indeed symbolizes Earth's interior.

Again, however, I do not consider this signal as a reliable confirmation of the hypotheses (e.g., the 2029 impact). Observed correlation does not come with the meaning, meaning is formed behind the eye of a beholder and that is an universe that may or may not be well correlated with external reality. Perhaps the correlation has nothing to do with builders. God knows... One cannot deny, however, the multitude of signals in the analyses, making it hard to discard the possibility of deeper meaning. Ambiguity is here probably by *design*, perhaps to stimulate our imagination? Why did Jesus speak in parables? Why doesn't the universe just tell us what it actually means when it speaks to us? The answer is - because it usually cannot be as direct, and it cannot for a good reason. What kind of neurons [or neuron components] we would be without being trained to think and imagine? A mind that doesn't think and imagine is a mind that does not exist. Thinking soul is a living mind, non-thinking soul is a mindless spirit.

9 Conclusion

A lot of correlations were found in this paper but, at least for some, it may be hard to attribute them to conscious arrangement. However, equally, it is difficult to discard all these as meaningless coincidences. I believe the constructors of the pyramids were subconsciously guided to construct the pyramids exactly at these locations, just like the ancient prophets were guided to encode information about neurogenesis in their prophecies, such as those present in the Bible. Rather than meaningless coincidence, I interpret this as meaningful synchronicity.

A lot of ages have been calculated and, due to various interpretations and possibilities one cannot be highly confident in any date for the construction of the Great Pyramid. It's probably not older than 38 million years and not younger than 5000 years. In my opinion, most likely dates are either about 30000 years ago (one of the ages derived from the luminescence dating of the Giza Valley Temple, however, this age may represent another maintenance age) or about 1.5 million years ago (or, more precisely, the end of the last 3rd order cycle period, as these can be correlated with cataclysmic events).

In any case, I find it highly unlikely that Egyptians are the original builders

of the greatest Giza structures. In the context of correlation with neurogenesis, the exact dates of construction are not that relevant. The importance is in information that obviously is encoded in the pyramids. Not only is the Great Pyramid equal in size and shape to an Earth's neuron cell, its location encodes the ages of major mass extinctions - previous and the current one, across various interpretations. All this, together with Egyptian religion, is deeply correlated with planetary neurogenesis.

There exists a high amount of synchronicity here and the Great Pyramid highlights the importance of relativity (multiple interpretations) and is even telling us that we should not take the speed of *light* as absolute. I didn't, and that's why I could decode this signal.

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